

THE UNIVERSITY OF HAWAI‘I AT MĀNOA

Hydrographic Observations At the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution Hawaii Ocean Time-series Site: 2023 - 2024

by

Fernando Carvalho Pacheco¹, Fernando Santiago-Mandujano¹, James Potemra¹,
Albert Plueddemann², Robert Weller², Daniel Fitzgerald¹, and Nan Galbraith²

Wednesday 17th December, 2025

Data Report - 19

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School of Ocean and Earth Science and Technology
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In 2003, Robert Weller (Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution [WHOI]), Albert Plueddemann (WHOI), and Roger Lukas (The University of Hawaii [UH]) proposed to establish a long-term surface mooring at the Hawaii Ocean Time-series (HOT) Station ALOHA (22°45'N, 158°W) to provide sustained, high-quality air-sea fluxes and the associated upper ocean response as a coordinated part of the HOT program, and as an element of the global array of ocean reference stations supported by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's (NOAA) Office of Climate Observation.

With support from the NOAA and the National Science Foundation (NSF), the WHOI HOT Site (WHOTS) surface mooring has been maintained at Station ALOHA since August 2004. This project aims to record long-term, high-quality air-sea fluxes as a coordinated part of the HOT program and contribute to the goals of observing heat, freshwater, and chemical fluxes at a site representative of the oligotrophic North Pacific Ocean. The approach is to maintain a surface mooring outfitted for meteorological and oceanographic measurements at a site near Station ALOHA by successive mooring turnarounds. These observations will be used to investigate air-sea interaction processes related to climate variability.

The original mooring system is described in the mooring deployment and recovery cruise reports [Plueddemann *et al.*, 2006, Whelan *et al.*, 2007, Whelan *et al.*, 2008, Whelan *et al.*, 2010, Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024, Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024]. Briefly, a Surlyn foam surface buoy is equipped with meteorological instrumentation, including two complete Air-Sea Interaction Meteorological (ASIMET) systems, measuring air and sea surface temperatures, relative humidity, barometric pressure, wind speed and direction, incoming shortwave and longwave radiation, and precipitation [Hosom *et al.*, 1995, Colbo and Weller, 2009]. Complete surface meteorological measurements are recorded every minute, as required to compute air-sea fluxes of heat, freshwater, and momentum. Each ASIMET system also transmits hourly averages of the surface meteorological variables via the Argos satellite system. The mooring line is instrumented to collect time series of upper ocean temperatures, velocities, and salinities coincident with the surface forcing record. This mooring includes conductivity, salinity, and temperature recorders, two Vector Measuring Current Meters (VMCMs), and two Acoustic Doppler current profilers (ADCPs). See the WHOTS-19 mooring diagram in the Fig. 1.1.

The subsurface instrumentation is located to resolve the temporal variations of shear and stratification in the upper pycnocline to support the study of mixed layer entrainment. Experience with moored profiler measurements near Hawaii suggests that Richardson number estimates over 10 m scales are adequate. Salinity is essential to the stratification, as salt-stratified barrier layers are observed at HOT and in the region [Kara *et al.*, 2000]. Hence, we use Sea-Bird SeaCATs and MicroCATs with vertical separation ranging from 5 to 20 m to measure temperature and salinity. We use two ADCPs made by Teledyne RD Instruments to obtain current profiles across the entrainment zone and in the mixed layer zone. Both ADCPs are in an upward-looking configuration, one is at 125 m, using 4 m bins, and the other is at 47.5 m using 2 m bins. To provide near-surface velocity (where ADCP estimates are less reliable), we deploy two Vector Measuring Current Meters (VMCMs). The nominal mooring design is a balance between resolving extremes versus the typical annual cycling of the mixed layer [Plueddemann *et al.*, 2006, Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007]. A pair of Sea-Bird SeaCATs (SBE-16) or MicroCATs (SBE-37) have been included since the WHOTS-9 deployment (June 2012) to measure near-bottom temperature and salinity.

The WHOTS-19 mooring was deployed on June 17, 2023 (WHOTS-19 cruise) and was recovered on June 06, 2024 (WHOTS-20 cruise). Both cruises were carried out aboard the R/V Oscar Elton Sette. The WHOTS-20 mooring

WHOTS 19

MAX. DIA. BUOY WATCH CIRCLE = 4.4 N.Miles

Position: Put in later

WHOTS MOORING

19th Deployment - v1

RG 12/29/22

Fig. 1.1: WHOTS-19 mooring design

was deployed on June 02, 2024, during the [WHOTS-20 cruise](#) and was recovered on September 28, 2025.

This report documents and describes the oceanographic observations made on the WHOTS-19 mooring for nearly one year and from shipboard measurements during the two cruises when the mooring was deployed and recovered. Sections [II](#) and [III](#) include a detailed description of the cruises and the mooring, respectively. Sampling and processing procedures of the hydrographic casts, thermosalinograph, and shipboard ADCP data collected during these cruises are described in Section [IV](#). Section [V](#) includes the processing procedures for the data collected by the moored instruments: [SeaCATs](#), [MicroCATs](#), [Moored ADCPs](#) and [VMCM](#). Plots of the resulting data and preliminary analysis are presented in Section [VI](#).

Description of the WHOTS-19 Mooring Cruises

2.1 WHOTS-19 Cruise: WHOTS-19 Mooring Deployment

The Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution Upper Ocean Processes Group (WHOI/UOP) with the UH group’s assistance, conducted the 19th deployment of the WHOTS mooring onboard the Oscar Elton Sette during the WHOTS-19 cruise between June 15 and June 22, 2023. The WHOTS-19 mooring was deployed at Station 50 on June 17, 2023, 02:59 UTC at 22°46.057’N, 157°53.964’W, and the WHOTS-18 mooring was recovered on June 19, 2023. The scientific personnel that participated during the cruise are listed in [Table 2.1](#).

Table 2.1: Scientific personnel on Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-19 deployment cruise.

Name	Title or function	Affiliation
Plueddeman, Albert	Chief Scientist	WHOI
Bigorre, Sebastien	Research Specialist	WHOI
Graham, Raymond	Research Associate	WHOI
Llanos, Eduardo	Research Technician	WHOI
Santiago-Mandujano, Fernando	Research Associate	UH
Fitzgerald, Dan	Marine Electronics Technician	UH
Rohrer, Tully	Research Associate	UH
Maloney, Kelsey	HIMB Housing Coordinator	UH
Adkison, Camille	Research Assistant	UH
Dale, Elizabeth	Research Technician	WHOI

The UH group conducted the shipboard oceanographic observations during the cruise. A complete description of these operations is available in the WHOTS-19 cruise report [[Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024](#)].

A Sea-Bird CTD (Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth) system was used to collect temperature (T), salinity (S), and dissolved oxygen (O₂) profiles during CTD casts. The time, location, and maximum pressure for each cast are listed in [table-2](#). A total of five CTD casts were conducted during the WHOTS-19 cruise between June 16 and June 19. CTD profiles were obtained at Station 20 (while in transit to the WHOTS mooring) and Station 52 (near the WHOTS-18 buoy). The cast at Station 20 reached a depth of approximately 1500 m and included three acoustic releases—two designated for the WHOTS-19 mooring and one backup—attached to the rosette frame for functional testing. Four CTD yo-yo casts were conducted at Station 52 to obtain repeated upper-ocean profiles for comparison with subsurface instruments on the WHOTS-18 mooring prior to its recovery. These casts were initiated approximately 0.25 nautical miles from the buoy and included multiple up-and-down cycles between the surface and depths of 200 to 215 meters, with varying drift during each cast. CTD modulo errors began to appear during casts 3 and 4, indicating intermittent communication issues between the CTD and the deck unit. The frequency of these errors increased substantially during subsequent casts near the WHOTS-19 mooring, ultimately leading to aborted casts. The issue persisted even after re-terminating the CTD cable and replacing the primary CTD with a spare unit, suggesting the fault likely resided in the CTD wire or the slip-rings. As a result, no CTD

casts could be completed near the WHOTS-19 mooring.

Between 2 and 4 water samples were taken from all casts. These samples were to be analyzed for salinity at UH and used to calibrate the CTD conductivity sensors.

Table 2.2: CTD stations occupied during the WHOTS-19 cruise
(Datetime is in mm/dd/yyyy hh:mm)

Station/cast	Date	In-water Time	Location	Maximum pressure (dbar)
20/1	06/16/2023	07:01	21°28.052'N, 158°21.087'W	1489
52/1	06/18/2023	16:05	22°40.680'N, 157°58.892'W	215
52/2	06/18/2023	20:02	22°40.888'N, 157°58.803'W	203
52/3	06/19/2023	00:05	22°40.707'N, 157°58.954'W	202
52/4	06/19/2023	05:22	22°41.226'N, 157°58.574'W	200

Also, continuous ADCP and near-surface thermosalinograph data were obtained while underway.

The R/V Oscar Elton Sette was equipped with a RDI Ocean Surveyor 75 kHz ADCP, set to function in broadband and narrowband configurations. The configuration information is shown in Table 2.3. The ADCP used input from a SAMOS gyrometer and Furuno GP 150, a GPS receiver, to establish the ship’s heading and attitude.

Table 2.3: Configuration of the Ocean Surveyor 75kHz ADCP on board the Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-19 cruise

Parameters	OS75BB	OS75NB
Sample interval (s)	300	300
Number of bins	80	55
Bin Length (m)	8	16
Transducer depth (m)	5	5
Blanking length (m)	8	8

Near-surface temperature and salinity data during the WHOTS-19 cruise were collected using the thermosalinograph (TSG) system installed aboard the NOAA Ship Oscar Elton Sette. The system sampled seawater from the ship’s continuous intake line and included the following instruments: an SBE-21 thermosalinograph (SN 3168), an SBE-45 micro-thermosalinograph (SN 0290), and an external SBE-38 temperature sensor (SN 212). The SBE-21 and SBE-45 units, each equipped with internal temperature and conductivity sensors, were located in the ship’s chemistry lab, approximately 70 meters from the hull intake. The SBE-38 was mounted externally at the seawater intake, positioned on the starboard side of the bow, forward of the bow thruster, at a depth of approximately 3 meters. All sensors recorded data every second. The system included a flow meter located in the chemistry lab, which indicated a flow rate of approximately 1.1 liters per minute throughout the cruise. Among the instruments, only the SBE-45 was equipped with a debubbler. To validate and correct for potential drift in salinity measurements, seawater samples were collected from the chemistry lab exhaust line every 8 hours. These samples were stored in 0.25-liter glass bottles and analyzed post-cruise at the University of Hawai’i laboratory.

2.2 WHOTS-20 Cruise: WHOTS-19 Mooring Recovery

The WHOI/UOP group carried out the mooring turnaround operations during the WHOTS-20 cruise, which took place from May 31 to June 8, 2024. The WHOTS-20 mooring was successfully deployed at Station 52 on June 2, 2024, at 03:54 UTC, at coordinates 22°40.08N, 157°57.01W. The WHOTS-19 mooring was recovered on June 6, 2024, at 18:50 UTC. The scientific personnel who participated in the cruise are listed in Table 2.4.

Table 2.4: Scientific personnel on Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-20 deployment cruise.

Name	Title or function	Affiliation
Bigorre, Sebastien	Chief Scientist	WHOI
Llanos, Nico	Engineer	WHOI
Graham, Raymond	Engineer	WHOI
Fitzgerald, Dan	Marine Electronics Technician	UH
Santiago-Mandujano, Fernando	Research Associate	UH
Rohrer, Tully	Research Associate	UH
Shepherd, Merritt	Research Assistant	UH
Maloney, Kelsey	HIMB Housing Coordinator	UH
Jandial, Prajna	Graduate Student	UH
Dirks, Jonah	Graduate Student	UH

The UH group conducted the shipboard oceanographic observations during the cruise. A complete description of these operations is available in the WHOTS-20 cruise report [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024].

A Sea-Bird CTD (Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth) system was used to collect temperature (T), salinity (S), and dissolved oxygen (O₂) profiles during CTD casts. The time, location, and maximum pressure for each cast are shown in Table 2.5.

Nine CTD casts were conducted during the WHOTS-20 cruise between June 1 and June 6, 2024. CTD profiles were collected at Station 20 (en route to the WHOTS mooring), Station 50 (near the WHOTS-19 buoy), and Station 52 (near the WHOTS-20 buoy). The cast at Station 20 reached a depth of approximately 1500m and included three acoustic releases—two intended for the WHOTS-20 mooring and one backup—secured to the rosette frame for functionality testing. This cast exhibited anomalous values in the primary temperature, conductivity, and oxygen sensors. Post-cast inspection revealed that the CTD pump cable had been pinched beneath a hose clamp on one of the Niskin bottles. The secondary sensor suite was unaffected. Four CTD yo-yo casts were conducted near the WHOTS-19 mooring prior to recovery to provide comparison profiles for the subsurface instruments, and three additional yo-yo casts were conducted near the WHOTS-20 mooring after deployment. All yo-yo casts began approximately 0.25 nautical miles from the buoys and consisted of five vertical cycles between 5m and 205m depth, with varying drift during each cast.

The first two yo-yo casts near the WHOTS-19 mooring (S50C1 and S50C2) displayed anomalous data at the start of each profile, likely due to air bubbles in the CTD plumbing system. These artifacts disappeared below 100m. A Y-shaped plastic “de-bubbler” was subsequently installed in both CTD plumbing lines to mitigate this issue. All subsequent casts returned high-quality data.

One deep CTD cast was conducted approximately 2 nautical miles from the WHOTS-19 buoy to obtain a profile for comparison with the near-bottom MicroCAT sensors. This cast reached a maximum depth of nearly 4550m. However, due to the absence of a functioning altimeter onboard, it was not possible to safely approach the depth of the deepest MicroCATs, located at approximately 4659m.

Between four and five water samples were collected during each cast using 0.25 liter glass bottles. These samples were returned to the University of Hawai‘i for salinity analysis and were used to calibrate the CTD conductivity sensors.

Table 2.5: CTD stations during the WHOTS-20 cruise (WHOTS-19 mooring recovery). Datetime is in UTC (mm/dd/yy hh:mm).

Station/cast	Date	In-water Time	Location	Maximum pressure (dbar)
20/1	6/1/2024	02:55	21°17.112N, 158°19.541W	1529
50/1	6/3/2024	16:07	22°46.880N, 157°55.793W	204
50/2	6/3/2024	20:04	22°46.221N, 157°56.073W	202
50/3	6/4/2024	00:08	22°46.396N, 157°56.165W	205
50/4	6/4/2024	04:02	22°46.339N, 157°56.148W	202
52/1	6/4/2024	20:37	22°40.237N, 157°59.375W	203
52/2	6/4/2024	23:58	22°40.237N, 157°59.271W	202
52/3	6/5/2024	04:04	22°40.430N, 157°59.022W	204
50/5	6/6/2024	00:09	22°47.311N, 157°57.818W	4625

Also, continuous ADCP and near-surface thermosalinograph data were obtained while underway.

The NOAA Ship Oscar Elton Sette was equipped with a Teledyne RDI Ocean Surveyor 75kHz Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP), configured to operate in narrowband mode. The broadband mode was non-functional during this cruise. Configuration details are provided in [Table 2.6](#). The ADCP relied on input from a SAMOS gyrometer and a Furuno GP-170 GPS receiver to determine the ship's heading and attitude.

Table 2.6: Configuration of the Ocean Surveyor 75kHz ADCP on board the Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-20 cruise

Parameters	OS75NB
Sample interval (s)	300
Number of bins	55
Bin Length (m)	16
Transducer depth (m)	5
Blanking length (m)	8

Near-surface salinity data during the WHOTS-20 cruise were collected using the thermosalinograph (TSG) system installed aboard the NOAA Ship Oscar Elton Sette. The system sampled water from the ship's continuous seawater supply and consisted of a Sea-Bird SBE-45 micro-thermosalinograph (SN 0290), equipped with internal temperature and conductivity sensors located in the ship's chemistry lab, approximately 70 meters from the hull intake.

A second TSG unit, the Sea-Bird SBE-21, was installed but was non-functional throughout the cruise. Similarly, the SBE-38 remote temperature sensor, mounted at the water intake near the ship's bow, was also inoperative. As a result, sea surface temperature data could not be collected during the cruise.

The SBE-45 recorded data at 1 Hz and included a built-in debubbler. The seawater intake is located at the bow of the vessel, forward of the starboard-side bow thruster, at a depth of 3 meters. Flow through the system was monitored via a flow meter in the chemistry lab, which registered a rate of approximately 1.5 liters per minute during the cruise.

To correct for potential drift in conductivity measurements, discrete salinity samples were collected every 8 hours from the exhaust line in the chemistry lab using 0.25-liter glass bottles. These samples were returned to the University of Hawai'i laboratory for post-cruise salinity analysis.

Description of WHOTS-19 Mooring

The WHOTS-19 mooring was deployed on June 17, 2023, from the NOAA Ship *Oscar Elton Sette* and recovered on June 6, 2024. The mooring consisted of a surface buoy equipped with two complete sets of Air–Sea Interaction Meteorological (ASIMET) sensors and a suite of subsurface oceanographic instruments mounted along the bridle and mooring line down to 155m, with additional sensors near the bottom. For a detailed technical description of the mooring design, see [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024, Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024].

The WHOTS-19 mooring was designed to collect high-quality time series of surface meteorology and upper-ocean temperature, salinity, and biogeochemical variables in support of long-term air-sea flux studies at Station ALOHA.

3.1 Surface Components

The buoy included the following instrumentation mounted on a blue hull with a white tower and yellow deck (Table 3.1):

Table 3.1: Surface meteorological instrumentation on the WHOTS-19 buoy, organized by system side (port = System 1, starboard = System 2). All sensors were mounted on the buoy tower. Heights are reported relative to the buoy deck.

Instrument Type	IDs / Details
Data Loggers	9 (System 1, port side); ID 42 (System 2, starboard side)
Relative Humidity and Air Temperature (HRH) Sensors	269 and 247, mounted at 231cm
Barometric Pressure Recorders (BPR)	210 and 206, mounted at 242cm
Wind Sensors (RM Young)	225 and 701, mounted at 264cm
Precipitation Sensors (PRC)	235 (System 1 – top broken before recovery); ID 506, both mounted at 256cm
Longwave Radiation Sensors (LWR)	214 and 219, mounted at 281cm
Shortwave Radiation Sensors (SWR)	233 and 373, mounted at 281cm
Sea Surface Temperature (SST)	1727 and 5996, mounted at –155cm
Iridium Satellite Systems	IMEIs: 300234063855630, 300234063160290
GPS – Melo	IMEI: 300034013707580
GPS – Rover	1034 and 724; IMEIs: 300434064530400, 300434063547190
Other Sensors	Vaisala WXT (ID 204, 264cm); Airmar (ID 6079L253, 273cm, hanging); HC2A (ID WI9, 232cm); SBE39AT (ID 719, 228cm)

3.2 Subsurface Instrumentation

Subsurface instruments were mounted along the bridle and at a fixed depth on the mooring line, as follows (Table 3.2):

Table 3.2: Additional shared surface instrumentation on the WHOTS-19 buoy, including GPS units, Iridium satellite modems, and auxiliary sensors.

Instrument Type	ID	Depth	Notes
MAPCO ₂ System	26	155	With equilibration tube
CTD (SBE16)	6832	155	
Oxygen Sensor	1381	155	
Fluorometer	2597	155	Includes bio-wiper
pH Sensor (SAMI)	P246	155	
Span Gas Canister	JB03812	—	For sensor calibration
Xeos Kilo Transmitter	1494	—	IMEI: 300234062727610

Five internally logging Sea-Bird SBE-56 temperature sensors were bolted to the buoy hull's underside, measuring sea surface temperature and salinity. The SBE-56s measured SST once every 60 sec between 80-110 cm below the surface. Two SBE-37 MicroCATs were at 1.55m measuring at every 300s (See Table 3.3).

Table 3.3: WHOTS-19 MicroCAT and SBE-56 Temperature Sensor Information.

Instrument	SN	Depth (m)	Sample Interval (sec)
SBE-56	6410	0.8	60
SBE-56	6239	0.8	60
SBE-56	6412	1.0	60
SBE-56	6983	1.1	60
SBE-56	7211	0.8	60
SBE-37	1727	1.55	300
SBE-37	5996	1.55	300

Instrumentation provided by UH for the WHOTS-19 mooring included 18 Sea-Bird SBE-37 MicroCATs, of which 9 were pressure-equipped. Two of them were installed approximately 39m above the anchor. All MicroCATs measured temperature and conductivity and were deployed with antifoulant capsules to minimize biofouling. In addition, UH deployed two upward-looking RDI Workhorse Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs) operating at 300kHz and 600kHz, respectively. WHOI contributed two Vector Measuring Current Meters (VMCMs), an Acoustic Receiver, and all required deep mooring hardware. The ADCPs were mounted at nominal depths of 47.5m and 125m, and the VMCMs were positioned at 10m and 30m.

The Table 3.4 table provides detailed metadata for the WHOTS-19 subsurface instrumentation, including nominal depths, serial numbers, sample intervals, and event times. To verify the performance of internal clocks, a cold-water spike was applied to all UH MicroCATs before deployment by placing an ice pack against each temperature sensor (Table 3.4) and again after recovery (Table 3.5). For the ADCPs, a 20-second manual transducer rub was performed to generate a recognizable signal spike (Table 3.6, Table 3.7).

Table 3.4: WHOTS-19 mooring subsurface instrument deployment. Times are UTC (MM/DD/YY hh:mm). Columns: SN = Serial Number, Inst = Instrument, Z = Depth (m), P SN = Pressure Sensor Serial Number, t = Sample Interval (s), CS = Cold Spike.

SN	Inst	Z	P	t	Start	CS Beg	CS End	In
3382	MC	7	N/A	180	06/13/23 23:59	06/16 00:00	06/16 00:30	06/16 21:00
0035	VMCM	10	N/A	60	06/08/23 00:21	06/16 20:23*	N/A	06/16 20:28
6892	MC	15	2651234	75	06/13/23 23:59	06/16 00:00	06/16 00:30	06/16 20:25
4663	MC	25	N/A	180	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 20:19
112497	AR	25	N/A	N/A	06/12/23 19:00	N/A	N/A	06/16 20:19
0058	VMCM	30	N/A	60	06/08/23 00:21	06/16 20:13*	N/A	06/16 20:16
3633	MC	35	N/A	180	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 20:12
3381	MC	40	N/A	180	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 20:09
3668	MC	45	5579	180	06/16/23 00:01	06/16 01:40	06/16 02:05	06/16 20:06
13917	ADCP	47.5	N/A	600	06/15/23 23:59	Table 3.6	Table 3.6	06/16 21:23
3619	MC	50	N/A	180	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 21:24
3620	MC	55	N/A	180	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 21:27
3621	MC	65	N/A	180	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 21:29
9988	MC	75	N/A	180	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 21:31
4699	MC	85	10209	240	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 21:32
3791	MC	95	N/A	180	06/16/23 02:00	06/16 02:06	06/16 02:30	06/16 21:34
2769	MC	105	12364705	240	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 21:36
25352	MC-N	120	5983494	240	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 21:47
7637	ADCP	125	N/A	300	06/15/23 23:59	Table 3.6	Table 3.6	06/16 21:47
25444	MC-N	135	12152941	240	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 21:49
4701	MC	155	10211	240	06/13/23 23:59	“	“	06/16 21:51
11381	MC	+39 m	2146836	300	06/16/23 00:01	“	“	06/17 00:02
11380	MC	+39 m	2146835	300	06/16/23 00:01	“	“	06/17 00:02

Table 3.5: WHOTS-19 mooring recovery summary for C-T (Conductivity-Temperature) and ADCP (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler) instruments. All times in UTC (MM/DD/YY hh:mm:ss). SN = Serial Number, Tlg = Logging, Spk = Spike, Q = Quality.

Z (m)	SN	T out	Spk	End Spk	Tlg Stop	N Samples	Q
7	3382	06/07/24 01:46:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/11/24 00:13:21	174243	Good
15	6892	06/07/24 01:54:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/14/24 14:38:03	414947	Good
25	4663	06/07/24 01:57:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/08/24 03:38:40	172873	Good
35	3633	06/07/24 00:41:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/07/24 19:31:30	172710	Good
40	3381	06/07/24 00:37:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/08/24 03:19:15	172866	Good
45	3668	06/07/24 00:33:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/08/24 03:07:45	171871	Good
47.5	ADCP 13917	06/07/24 00:29:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	N/A	40846	Stopped 3/25/24
50	3619	06/07/24 00:28:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/11/24 00:19:06	174245	Good
55	3620	06/07/24 00:27:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/11/24 00:01:23	174240	Good
65	3621	06/07/24 00:25:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/10/24 23:56:24	174238	Good
75	9988	06/07/24 00:25:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/07/24 20:19:00	172725	Good
85	4699	06/07/24 00:24:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/10/24 23:52:11	130678	Good
95	3791	06/07/24 00:24:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/07/24 04:30:20	171890	Good
105	2769	06/07/24 00:23:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/08/24 03:28:10	129653	Did not record P/C
120	25352	06/07/24 00:21:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/08/24 00:27:30	129607	Good
125	ADCP 7637	06/07/24 00:17:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/07/24 19:07:00	51522	Good
135	25444	06/07/24 00:16:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/07/24 22:42:30	129581	Good
155	4701	06/07/24 00:14:00	06/07/24 05:56:00	06/07/24 06:26:00	06/07/24 22:06:10	129571	Good
38 mab	11380	06/06/24 19:50:00	06/07/24 19:52:00	06/07/24 20:10:00	06/08/24 00:27:06	103093	Good
38 mab	11381	06/06/24 19:50:00	06/07/24 19:52:00	06/07/24 20:10:00	06/08/24 00:27:19	103093	Good

Table 3.6: WHOTS-19 mooring ADCP deployment and configuration information. All times are in UTC (MM/DD/YY hh:mm:ss).

Parameter	ADCP S/N 13917	ADCP S/N 7637
Frequency (kHz)	600	300
Number of Depth Cells	25	30
Depth Cell Size (m)	2 m	4 m
Pings per Ensemble	80	40
Time per Ensemble (min)	10 min	10 min
Time per Ping (sec)	2 sec	4 sec
Time of First Ping	06/15/2023, 23:59:00	06/15/2023, 23:59:00
Transducer 1 Spike Time	06/16/2023, 05:40:00	06/16/2023, 05:40:00
Transducer 2 Spike Time	06/16/2023, 05:40:15	06/16/2023, 05:40:15
Transducer 3 Spike Time	06/16/2023, 05:40:30	06/16/2023, 05:40:30
Transducer 4 Spike Time	06/16/2023, 05:40:45	06/16/2023, 05:40:45
Ice Spike Time Begin	06/16/2023, 00:00:00	06/16/2023, 00:00:00
Ice Spike Time End	06/16/2023, 00:30:00	06/16/2023, 00:30:00
Time in Water	06/16/2023, 21:23:00	06/16/2023, 21:47:00
Depth (m)	47.5 m	125 m

Table 3.7: WHOTS-19 mooring ADCP recovery information. All times are in UTC (MM/DD/YY, hh:mm:ss).

Parameter	ADCP S/N 13917	ADCP S/N 7637
Frequency (kHz)	600	300
Number of Depth Cells	25	30
Depth Cell Size (m)	2 m	4 m
Pings per Ensemble	80	40
Time per Ensemble (min)	10 min	10 min
Time per Ping (sec)	2 sec	4 sec
Time of Last Ping	06/07/24, 05:40:00	06/07/24, 05:40:00
Transducer 1 Spike Time	06/07/24, 07:32:00	06/07/24, 07:21:00
Transducer 2 Spike Time	06/07/24, 07:32:15	06/07/24, 07:21:15
Transducer 3 Spike Time	06/07/24, 07:32:30	06/07/24, 07:21:30
Transducer 4 Spike Time	06/07/24, 07:32:45	06/07/24, 07:21:45
Ice Spike Start Time	06/07/24, 05:56:00	06/07/24, 05:56:00
Ice Spike End Time	06/07/24, 06:26:00	06/07/24, 06:26:00
Time in the Water	06/16/23, 21:47:00	06/16/23, 21:47:00
Time out of Water	06/07/24, 00:29:00	06/07/24, 00:17:00
Depth (m)	47.5 m	125 m

The 300 kHz ADCP at 125 m (SN 7637) operated flawlessly for the entire deployment and was still recording on recovery. In contrast, the 600 kHz ADCP at 47.5 m (SN 13917) stopped logging on 25 March 2024. Data collected are good, aside from near-surface side-lobe interference.

The RDI 300 kHz Workhorse Sentinel ADCP, SN 7637, was installed at 125 m with its transducers facing upward and an external battery pack. It pinged every 4 s for 160 s once every 10 min—a burst regime selected to reduce aliasing from large-swell orbital motions. Bin size was 4 m. In total, 51 522 ensembles were logged, beginning 06/15/2023 23:59:00 and ending 06/07/2024 18:48:59 (see [Table 3.6](#), [Table 3.7](#), and [WHOTS-19 300 kHz - Serial 7367](#)). This instrument also measured temperature.

The RDI 600 kHz Workhorse Sentinel ADCP, SN 13917, was installed at 47.5 m with transducers facing upward and an external battery pack. It pinged every 2 s for 160 s once every 10 min, with a 2 m bin size. The instrument logged 40 846 ensembles between 06/15/2023 23:59:00 and 03/25/2024 15:38:59 (see [Table 3.6](#), [Table 3.7](#), and [WHOTS-19 600 kHz - Serial 13917](#)). Upon recovery it was silent. Diagnostic checks suggest a Y-cable fault: the internal battery was fully depleted, whereas both external packs were only partially discharged—an imbalance not expected under normal operation. Data collected before shutdown are high-quality, apart from near-surface side-lobe interference. This instrument also measured temperature.

Two VMCMs (SN 0035 at 10 m and SN 0058 at 30 m) were configured by the WHOI/UOP group to sample every minute; both also recorded temperature.

Recovery details for the C-T instruments appear in [Table 3.5](#). All WHOTS-19 instruments were retrieved. Biofouling was common—severe near the surface and detectable, though minor, down to the 125 m ADCP.

Post-recovery inspection found every MicroCAT intact with its antifoulant capsule. High-quality records were obtained from all units except those flagged in [Table 3.5](#) (see [MicroCAT Data Processing Procedures](#), [MicroCAT Data](#)). One exception is SN 2769, which failed to log pressure and conductivity, although no external damage to the sensor or its conductivity cell was observed.

WHOTS (19-20) Cruise Shipboard Observations

The hydrographic profile observations made during the WHOTS cruises were obtained with a Sea-Bird CTD package with dual temperature, salinity, and oxygen sensors. This CTD was installed on a rosette sampler with 5 L Niskin sampling bottles for calibration water samples. Furthermore, the ship Oscar Sette came equipped with a thermosalinograph system that provided a continuous depiction of the near-surface layer's temperature and salinity. However near-surface temperatures were not available during the WHOTS-20 cruise, because the thermosalinograph remote temperature sensor was not functional. Horizontal currents over the depth range of 30-700 m were measured from the shipboard 75 kHz Ocean Surveyor (OS75) ADCP (narrowband) with a vertical resolution of 16m for the WHOTS-19 and WHOTS-20 cruises. Broadband mode for the OS75 provided additional current data over the range upper 200 m with a vertical resolution of 8m. Unfortunately, the broadband mode was non-functional during WHOTS-20.

Data gaps occurred when the system was shut down temporarily during communications with the acoustic releases used for the moorings during both cruises. Periods of missing data between 300 and 450 m in the broadband ADCP were apparent due to the lack of scattering material in the water.

4.1 Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth (CTD) Profiling

Continuous measurements of temperature, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, and pressure were made with the UH Sea-Bird SBE-9/11Plus CTD underwater units #1506 and #1487 during WHOTS-19 cruise and #0895 during WHOTS-20 cruise. The CTD was equipped with an internal Digiquartz pressure sensor and pairs of external temperature, conductivity, and oxygen sensors.

Each temperature-conductivity sensor pair used a Sea-Bird TC duct, which circulated seawater through independent pump and plumbing installations. The CTD configuration also included two oxygen sensors, installed in the plumbing for each sensor set. In both cruises, the CTD was mounted in a vertical position in the lower part of a rosette sampler, with the sensors' water intakes located at the bottom of the rosette.

The package was deployed on a conducting cable, which allowed for real-time data acquisition and display. The deployment procedure consisted of lowering the package to approximately 10 dbar and waiting until the CTD pumps started operating. The CTD was then raised until the sensors were close to the surface to begin the CTD cast. The time and position of each cast were obtained via a GPS connection to the CTD deck box. Four salinity samples were taken on each cast for calibration of the conductivity sensors.

4.1.1 Data Acquisition and Processing

CTD data were acquired at the instrument's highest sampling rate of 24 samples per second. Digital data were stored on a laptop computer, and, for redundancy, the analog signal was recorded on a separate computer using a sound card and Audacity (TM) software. Backups of CTD data were made onto USB storage cards.

The raw CTD data were quality controlled and screened for spikes described in the WHOTS Data Report 1 [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007]. Data alignment, averaging, correction, and reporting were done as described in [Tupas *et al.*, 1993]. Spikes in the data occur when the CTD samples the disturbed water of its wake. Therefore, the downcast samples were rejected when the CTD was moving upward or when its acceleration exceeded 0.5 m s⁻² in magnitude. The data were subsequently averaged into 2-dbar pressure bins after calibrating the CTD conductivity with the bottle salinities.

The data were additionally screened by comparing the T-C sensor pairs. These differences permitted the identification of problems with the sensors. The data from only one T-C pair, whichever was deemed most reliable, is reported here. Only data from the downcast are reported, as wake effects from the rosette commonly contaminate upcast data.

Temperature is reported on the ITS-90 scale. Salinity and all derived units were calculated using the UNESCO (1981) routines; salinity is reported in the Practical Salinity(SA) scale (PSS-78). Oxygen is reported in $\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$.

4.1.2 CTD Sensor Calibration and Corrections

4.1.2.1 Pressure

The pressure calibration strategy for CTD pressure transducers #154451 and #53702 used during WHOTS-19 and #101430 used during WHOTS-20 cruise employed a high-quality quartz pressure transducer as a transfer standard. Periodic recalibrations of this lab standard were performed with a primary pressure standard. The only corrections applied to the CTD pressures were a constant offset determined when the CTD first enters the water on each cast. Also, a span correction determined from bench tests on the sensor against the transfer standard was applied. These procedures and corrections are thoroughly documented in the HOT-2022 data report [Fujieki *et al.*, 2024] and HOT-2023 data report [Fujieki *et al.*, 2025].

4.1.2.2 Temperature/Conductivity

Sea-Bird SBE-3-Plus temperature and SBE 4C conductivity transducers were used during WHOTS-19 and -20 cruises. These sensors' history and performance have been monitored during HOT cruises, and calibrations and drift corrections applied during WHOTS cruises are thoroughly documented in the HOT-2022 data report [Fujieki *et al.*, 2024] and HOT-2023 data report [Fujieki *et al.*, 2025].

4.1.2.3 Dissolved Oxygen

Sea-Bird SBE-43 oxygen sensors were used during the WHOTS-19 and -20 cruises. The WHOTS-19 oxygen data were calibrated using calibration coefficients obtained during the HOT-342 cruise conducted on 24-30 May 2023, before the WHOTS-19 cruise, which used the same primary oxygen sensor. The CTD empirical calibration was performed using oxygen water samples and the procedure from [Owens and Millard, 1985]. See [Tupas *et al.*, 1996] for details on these calibrations procedures. The oxygen data from WHOTS-20 were calibrated using calibration coefficients obtained during the HOT-350 cruise conducted on April 27 to May 1, 2024 before the WHOTS-20 cruise, which used the same oxygen sensors.

4.2 Water Sampling and Analysis

4.2.1 Salinity

Salinity samples were collected by a rosette sampler during CTD casts at selected depths during WHOTS-19 and -20, and then sub-sampled in 250 ml glass bottles. The top of each bottle and thimble were thoroughly dried before being tightly capped to prevent water from being trapped between the cap or thimble and the bottle’s mouth. It has been observed that residual water trapped in this way increases its salinity due to evaporation, and it can leak into the sample when the bottle is opened for measuring. Samples from each cruise were measured after the cruise in the UH laboratory using a Guildline Autosol 8400B SN 73647 for WHOTS-19 and WHOTS-20. International Association for Physical Sciences of the Ocean (IAPSO) standard seawater samples were measured to standardize the Autosol, and samples from a large batch of “secondary standard” (substandard) seawater were measured after every 24-48 samples to detect drift in the Autosol. Standard deviations of the secondary standard measurements were less than ± 0.001 for WHOTS-19 and -20 cruises [Table 4.1](#).

The substandard water was collected by a rosette sampler from 1020 m at station ALOHA during HOT cruises and drained into a 50-liter Nalgene plastic carboy. In the laboratory, the water was then thoroughly mixed in a glass carboy for 20 minutes by manually shaking, rolling, and tilting the carboy vigorously, after which a 2-inch protective layer of white oil was added on top to deter evaporation. The substandard water was allowed to stand for approximately three days before it was used and was stored in the same temperature-controlled room as the Autosol, protecting it from the light with black plastic bags to inhibit biological growth. Substandard seawater batch #74 was prepared on July 19, 2023, and it was used for WHOTS-19 (See [WHOTS-19 Salinity Measurements](#)). The batch #76 was prepared on April 11, 2024, and it was used for WHOTS-20 (See [WHOTS-20 Salinity Measurements](#)).

Samples from the WHOTS-19 were measured on October 28, 2019 and samples from WHOTS-20 were measured on September 13, 2021. [Table 4.1](#) shows the precision measurements of the secondary sub-standards.

Table 4.1: The precision of salinity measurements of secondary lab standards.

Cruise	Mean Salinity +/- SD	# Samples	Substandard Batch	IAPSO Batch
WHOTS-19	34.4954 \pm 0.0004	5	74	P166
WHOTS-20	34.4900 \pm 0.0001	2	76	P167

4.3 Thermosalinograph Data Acquisition and Processing

4.3.1 WHOTS-19 Cruise

Near-surface temperature and salinity data during the WHOTS-19 cruise were acquired from the thermosalinograph (TSG) system installed on the NOAA Ship Oscar Sette. The sensors were sampling water from the continuous seawater system running through the ship, and were comprised of one thermosalinograph model SBE-21 (SN 3168) and a micro-thermosalinograph model SBE-45 (SN 0290), both with (internal) temperature and conductivity sensors located in the ship’s chemistry lab, about 70 m from the hull intake; and an SBE-38 (SN 212) external temperature sensor located at the entrance of the water intake. All instruments recorded data every second. The water intake is located at the ship’s bow, forward from the starboard side bow thruster at a depth of 3 m. The system has a flow meter in the chemistry lab, showing a flow rate of about 1.1 liter/minute during the cruise. Only the SBE-45 has a debubbler. Salinity water samples were taken every 8 hours from the exhaust in the Chemistry lab using 0.25 liter glass bottles to be measured in the UH lab to correct for any drift in the thermosalinograph conductivities.

4.3.1.1 Temperature Calibration

External temperature data from the SBE-38 sensor (last calibrated at Sea-Bird on December 08, 2022) were used to measure the seawater temperature. These data were compared to the data collected during CTD casts.

4.3.1.2 Nominal Conductivity Calibration

Data from the SBE-45 conductivity and temperature sensors were used to calculate the intake seawater salinity. The SBE-45 was last calibrated on November 11, 2022, and the SBE21 sensor on December 29, 2022. All conductivity data from the thermosalinograph were nominally calibrated with coefficients from this calibration. However, all the final salinity data reported here were calibrated against bottle data, as explained below.

4.3.1.3 Data Processing

Daily files containing navigation data recorded every second were concatenated with the thermosalinograph data. The thermosalinograph data were then screened for gross errors, with upper and lower bounds of 18°C and 35°C for temperature and 3 and 6 S m⁻¹ for conductivity. There were no points outside the valid temperature range and no points outside the valid conductivity range.

A 5-point running median filter was used to detect one- or two-point temperature and conductivity glitches in the thermosalinograph data. Glitches in temperature and conductivity detected by the 5-point median filter were immediately replaced by the median. Threshold values of 0.3°C for temperature and 0.1 S m⁻¹ for conductivity were used for the median filter. After running the filter, there were 5 internal temperature, 0 external temperature, and 5 conductivity points replaced with the median.

A 3-point triangular running mean filter was used to smooth the temperature and conductivity data after passing the glitch detection.

The thermosalinograph aboard the Ship Oscar Sette was set to record data every second. Data were visually scanned to flag spikes likely caused by contamination due to the introduction of bubbles to the flow-through system during transits or rough conditions. Of 434647 data points, 11014 conductivity data points were flagged as bad.

4.3.1.4 Bottle salinity and CTD Salinity Comparisons

The thermosalinograph salinity was calibrated by comparing it to bottle salinity samples drawn from a water intake next to the thermosalinograph every 8 hours throughout the cruise. Of the twenty thermosalinograph bottles sampled, no casts were identified as a conductivity outlier. Samples were analyzed as described in [Water Sampling and Analysis](#). The comparison was made in conductivity to eliminate the effects of temperature. The conductivity of each bottle sample was computed using the salinity of the bottle, thermosalinograph temperature, and a pressure of 10 dbar, which includes the pressure of the flow-through system's pump.

Salinity samples were drawn from the flow-through system, located less than 0.5 m from the SBE-45. Consequently, there should be virtually no delay between when the water passes through the thermosalinograph and sampled. A 90-second average centered on the sample draw time was chosen for processing purposes.

In order to make the comparison in conductivity units, the CTD conductivity was calculated using the 4 dbar downcast CTD salinity, the internal thermosalinograph temperature, and a pump pressure of 10 dbar. There were five CTD casts conducted during WHOTS-19 while the thermosalinograph was running. No casts were removed from the analysis as temperature and conductivity outliers.

A cubic spline was fit to the time series of the differences between the bottle and TSG conductivity, and a correction was obtained for the TSG conductivities. Salinity was calculated using these corrected conductivities, the thermosalinograph temperatures, and 10 dbar pressure. After applying corrections, the mean difference between the bottle and thermosalinograph salinities was 0.0001 psu with a standard deviation of 0.0044 psu. The mean CTD - thermosalinograph difference was 0.0077 psu with a standard deviation of 0.0150 psu.

4.3.1.5 CTD Temperature Comparisons

There were five CTD casts conducted during WHOTS-19, one of which was a test cast offshore Honolulu (Station 20) and four at Station 52, respectively. The 3 dbar downcast CTD temperature data from those casts were used to compare with the thermosalinograph data at the time of the casts. This comparison gives an estimate of the quality of the thermosalinograph measurements. Of the 5 casts, none was identified as temperature outliers after comparing it against the thermosalinograph data. The mean difference between the CTD and the internal temperature sensor was -0.2114°C , with a standard deviation of $\pm 0.0183^{\circ}\text{C}$.

4.3.2 WHOTS-20 Cruise

Near-surface salinity data during the WHOTS-20 cruise were acquired from the thermosalinograph (TSG) system installed on the NOAA Ship Oscar Sette. The instrument was sampling water from the continuous seawater system running through the ship, and was comprised of one micro-thermosalinograph model SBE-45 (SN 0290), with (internal) temperature and conductivity sensors located in the ship's chemistry lab, about 70 m from the hull intake. Another thermosalinograph model SBE-21 also installed on the system was not working during the cruise. Also not working was the SBE-38 remote temperature sensor located at the entrance of the water intake, and consequently we were not able to collect sea-water temperatures during the cruise. The SBE-45 thermosalinograph was recording data every second. The water intake is located at the ship's bow, forward from the starboard side bow thruster at a depth of 3 m. The system has a flow meter in the chemistry lab, showing a flow rate of about 1.5 liter/minute during the cruise, and the SBE-45 has a debubbler. Salinity water samples were taken every 8 hours from the exhaust in the Chemistry lab using 0.25 liter glass bottles to be measured in the UH lab to correct for any drift in the thermosalinograph conductivities.

4.3.2.1 Temperature Calibration

External temperature data from the SBE-38 sensor was not collected during this cruise.

4.3.2.2 Nominal Conductivity Calibration

Data from the SBE-45 conductivity and temperature sensors were used to calculate the intake seawater salinity. These sensors were last calibrated at Sea-Bird on November 11, 2022. All conductivity data from the thermosalinograph were nominally calibrated with coefficients from this calibration. However, all the final salinity data reported here were calibrated against bottle data, as explained below.

4.3.2.3 Data Processing

Daily files containing navigation data recorded every second were concatenated with the thermosalinograph data. The thermosalinograph data were then screened for gross errors, with upper and lower bounds of 18°C and 35°C for temperature and 3 and 6 S m^{-1} for conductivity. There were 488 points outside the valid temperature range and no points outside the valid conductivity range.

A 5-point running median filter was used to detect one- or two-point temperature and conductivity glitches in the thermosalinograph data. Glitches in temperature and conductivity detected by the 5-point median filter were immediately replaced by the median. Threshold values of 0.3°C for temperature and 0.1 S m^{-1} for conductivity were used for the median filter. After running the filter, there was no internal temperature, no external temperature. There were 25 conductivity points replaced by the median. A 3-point triangular running mean filter was used to smooth the temperature and conductivity data after passing the glitch detection.

The thermosalinograph aboard the Ship Oscar Sette was set to record data every second. Both thermosalinographs exhibited a number of conductivity and temperature glitches due to air going into the plumbing.

Data set was visually scanned to flag spikes likely caused by contamination due to the introduction of bubbles to the flow-through system during transits or rough conditions. Of 705386 data points, 137989 conductivity data points were flagged as bad.

4.3.2.4 Bottle salinity and CTD Salinity Comparisons

The thermosalinograph salinity was calibrated by comparing it to bottle salinity samples drawn from a water intake next to the thermosalinograph every 8 hours throughout the cruise. Of the twenty-four thermosalinograph bottles sampled, no bottles were identified as a conductivity outlier. Samples were analyzed as described in [Water Sampling and Analysis](#). The comparison was made in conductivity to eliminate the effects of temperature. The conductivity of each bottle sample was computed using the salinity of the bottle, thermosalinograph temperature, and a pressure of 10 dbar, which includes the pressure of the flow-through system’s pump.

Salinity samples were drawn from the flow-through system, located less than 0.5 m from the SBE-45. Consequently, there should be virtually no delay between when the water passes through the thermosalinograph and sampled. A 90-second average centered on the sample draw time was chosen for processing purposes.

In order to make the comparison in conductivity units, the CTD conductivity was calculated using the 3 dbar downcast CTD salinity, the internal thermosalinograph temperature, and a pump pressure of 10 dbar. There were nine CTD casts conducted during WHOTS-20 while the thermosalinograph was running. Cast two was removed from the analysis as temperature and conductivity outlier.

A cubic spline was fit to the time series of the differences between the bottle and TSG conductivity, and a correction was obtained for the TSG conductivities. Salinity was calculated using these corrected conductivities, the thermosalinograph temperatures, and ten dbar pressure. After applying corrections, the mean difference between the bottle and thermosalinograph salinities was less than -1 mpsu with a standard deviation of 0.0119 psu. The mean CTD - thermosalinograph difference was 0.0087 psu with a standard deviation of 0.0461 psu.

4.3.2.5 CTD Temperature Comparisons

There were nine CTD casts conducted during WHOTS-20, one of which was a test cast offshore Honolulu (Station 20), five at Station 50 (near the WHOTS-19 buoy), and 3 at Station 52 (near the WHOTS-20 buoy). The 3 dbar downcast CTD temperature data from those casts were used to compare with the thermosalinograph data at the time of the casts. This comparison gives an estimate of the quality of the thermosalinograph measurements. Of the nine casts, cast two was identified as temperature outlier after comparing it against the thermosalinograph data and removed from the analysis. The mean difference between the CTD and the internal temperature sensor was -0.1399°C , with a standard deviation of $\pm 0.0527^{\circ}\text{C}$.

4.4 Shipboard ADCP

4.4.1 WHOTS-19 Deployment Cruise

Currents were measured for the cruise duration over the depth range of 30-700 m with a 75 kHz RDI Ocean Surveyor (OS75) ADCP working in narrowband mode with a vertical resolution of 16 m and broadband mode with a vertical resolution of 8 m. The system yielded good data [[Santiago-Mandujano et al., 2024](#)] during operations near the WHOTS-18 and WHOTS-19 moorings. The broadband system only recorded good data in the upper 200 m. The times of the datasets from the OS75 kHz are shown in [Table 4.2](#).

Table 4.2: ADCP record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss) for the narrowband and broadband 75 kHz ADCP during the WHOTS-19 cruise

WHOTS-19	OS75nb	OS75bb
File starting time	06/16/23 02:12:16	06/16/23 02:12:16
File ending time	06/22/23 18:17:13	06/22/23 18:17:13

4.4.2 WHOTS-20 Deployment Cruise

Currents were measured for the duration of the cruise over the depth range of 30-700 m with a 75 kHz RDI Ocean Surveyor (OS75) ADCP working in narrowband mode with a vertical resolution of 16 m. Unfortunately the broadband mode was non-functional during WHOTS-20. The narrowband system yielded good data (see [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024]) during operations near the WHOTS-19 and WHOTS-20 moorings. The times of the datasets from the OS75 kHz are shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: ADCP record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss) for the narrowband 75 kHz ADCP during the WHOTS-20 cruise

WHOTS-20	OS75nb	OS75bb
File starting time	05/31/24 22:21:54	N/A
File ending time	06/08/24 18:08:47	N/A

Moored Instrument Observations

5.1 MicroCAT Data Processing Procedures

Each moored MicroCAT temperature, conductivity, and pressure (when installed) was calibrated at Sea-Bird before their deployment and after their recovery on the dates shown in [Table 5.1](#). The internally-recorded data from each instrument were downloaded on board the ship after the mooring recovery. The nominally-calibrated data were plotted for a visual assessment of the data quality. The data processing included checking the internal clock data against external event times, pressure sensor drifts correction, temperature sensor stability, and conductivity calibration against CTD data from casts conducted near the mooring during HOT and WHOTS cruises. The detailed processing procedures are described in this section. Individual configurations for the MicroCATs on the WHOTS-19 mooring are detailed in [WHOTS-19 MicroCAT - Headers](#).

Table 5.1: WHOTS-19 MicroCAT temperature sensor calibration dates and sensor drift during deployments; *SN* = *Sea-Bird Serial Number*; *PDC* = *Pre-Deployment Calibration*; *PRC* = *Post-Recovery Calibration*; *TSA* = *Temperature Sensor's Annual Drift during WHOTS-19* ; *N. depth* = *Nominal deployment depth*

N. depth (m)	SN	PDC	PRC	TSA(mili °C)
1.6	1727	01-Mar-2023	16-Aug-2024	-1.34
1.6	5996	26-Feb-2023	16-Aug-2024	-1.06
7	3682	14-Apr-2023	27-Oct-2024	-0.92
15	6892	14-Apr-2023	20-Oct-2024	0.67
25	4663	14-Apr-2023	18-Oct-2024	0.17
35	3633	14-Apr-2023	27-Oct-2024	-0.66
40	3381	14-Apr-2023	27-Oct-2024	0.29
45	3668	14-Apr-2023	07-Nov-2024	-0.41
50	3619	18-Apr-2023	27-Oct-2024	0.15
55	3620	14-Apr-2023	13-Nov-2024	-0.87
65	3621	13-Apr-2023	12-Nov-2024	-0.39
75	9988	14-Apr-2023	23-Oct-2024	-0.22
85	4699	18-Apr-2023	15-Nov-2024	0.14
95	3791	13-Apr-2023	18-Oct-2024	0.31
105	2769	14-Apr-2023	19-Oct-2024	-0.26
120	25352	29-Dec-2022	24-Oct-2024	0.23
135	25444	30-Dec-2022	24-Oct-2024	-0.64
155	4701	18-Apr-2023	20-Oct-2024	0.18
4665	11381	10-Feb-2023	20-Aug-2024	0.87
4665	11380	15-Feb-2023	20-Aug-2024	-0.35

5.1.1 Internal Clock Check and Missing Samples

Before the WHOTS-19 mooring deployment and after its recovery (before the data logging was stopped), the MicroCATs temperature sensors were placed in contact with an ice pack to create a spike in the data, to check for any problems with their internal clocks, and for possible missing samples (Table 3.5). The cold spikes deployment were detected by a sudden decrease in temperature. For all the instruments, the clock time of this event matched the time of the spike (within the sampling interval of each instrument) correctly. The instrument SN 2769 failed to record pressure and conductivity, although nothing was visibly wrong with this instrument or its conductivity cell after recovery. The instrument was repaired at Sea-Bird in March, 2025 and it is back in working conditions.

5.1.2 Pressure Drift Correction and Pressure Variability

Some MicroCATs used in the moorings were outfitted with pressure sensors (Table 3.5). Biases were detected in the pressure sensors by comparing the on-deck pressure readings (which should be zero for standard atmospheric pressure) before deployment and after recovery. Table 5.2 shows the magnitude of the bias for each of the sensors before and after deployment. To correct this offset, a linear fit between the initial and final on-deck pressure offset as a function of time was obtained and subtracted from each sensor. Fig. 5.1 shows the linearly corrected pressures measured by the MicroCATs located above 200 m during the WHOTS-18 deployment. For all these sensors, the mean difference from the nominal instrument pressure (based on the deployed depth) was less than 1.5 dbar. The standard deviation of the pressure for the duration of the record was less than 1 dbar for all sensors, with the deeper sensors showing a slightly larger standard deviation. The range of variability for all sensors was about ± 3 dbar.

The causes of pressure variability can be several, including density variations in the water column above the instrument; horizontal dynamic pressure (not only due to the currents but also due to the motion of the mooring); mooring position [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007].

Table 5.2: Pressure bias of MicroCATs with pressure sensors for WHOTS-19. SN = Sea-bird Serial Number; BBD = Bias Before Deployment (dbar); BAR = Bias After Recovery (dbar)

Depth (m)	SN	BBD(dbar)	BAR(dbar)
15	6892	-0.09	-0.10
45	3668	-0.06	-0.12
85	4699	-0.11	-0.09
120	25352	0.11	1.13
135	25444	0.04	-0.64
155	4701	-1.62	-1.63
4665	11381	-2.06	-1.02
4665	11380	0.54	1.35

5.1.3 Temperature Sensor Stability

The MicroCAT temperature sensors were calibrated at Sea-Bird before and after each deployment, and their annual drift evaluations based on these calibrations are shown in Table 5.1. These values turned out to be insignificant (not higher than 0.0015 °C) for all sensors. Comparisons between the MicroCAT and CTD data from casts conducted near the mooring during HOT cruises confirmed that the rest of the moored instruments' temperature drift was insignificant. The temperatures from the two MicroCATs (SN 11381 and SN 11380) deployed near the bottom were drift corrected. Fig. 5.7 (upper panel) shows the temperature differences between both instruments before and after the correction. After the correction, the temperature differences were in the ± 0.001 °C range.

Temperature comparisons between one of the WHOTS-19 near-surface MicroCAT (SN 1727) and the four SBE-56 surface temperature sensors in the buoy hull Table 3.3 are shown in Fig. 5.2. All the SBE-56 instruments returned full records, and none of them show any obvious bias compared to the Microcat measurements.

In addition to the Sea-Bird temperature sensors, there were additional temperature sensors in the VMCMs (at 10 and 30 m) and in the ADCPs (at 47.5 m and 125 m). Comparisons with the temperatures from adjacent MicroCATs were conducted to evaluate the temperatures from those sensors.

Fig. 5.1: Linearly corrected pressures from MicroCATs between 7 and 155 m during WHOTS-19 deployment. The horizontal dashed line is the sensor’s nominal pressure, based on deployed depth. The text on the left (right) side of the figure indicates the mean (standard deviation) of the difference between each instrument’s pressure and nominal pressure.

Fig. 5.2: The temperature difference between MicroCAT SN 1727 at 1 m, and near-surface temperature sensors SN 6410 (top panel), 6239 (second panel), 6412 (third panel), 6983 (fourth panel), and 7211 (bottom panel) during the WHOTS-19 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.

5.1.3.1 Comparisons with VMCM and ADCP temperature sensors

The upper panel of Fig. 5.3 shows the difference between the 10-m VMCM and the 7-m MicroCAT temperatures during WHOTS-19, after adding a 0.03881°C offset correction to the VMCM. The offset was the mean difference between the uncorrected VMCM and the 7-m MicroCAT data. Also shown for comparison in the middle panel of the figure are the corrected VMCM temperature differences from the 15 m MicroCAT. The lower panel shows the temperature fluctuations in the differences between the 7 and 15-m MicroCATs, which seem to be around zero, with sporadic high excursions (nearly 0.6°C) from the 7 m MicroCAT.

Temperature differences between the 30-m VMCM and the adjacent MicroCATs at 25 and 35-m during WHOTS-19 are shown in Fig. 5.4. For comparison, the differences between the MicroCATs temperatures are also shown in the lower panel.

Temperature differences between the 47.5-m ADCP and the temperatures from adjacent MicroCATs at 45 and 50-m during WHOTS-19 are shown in Fig. 5.5. The 600kHz ADCP failed and stopped collecting data on March 25, 2024 (see *Description of WHOTS-19 Mooring*). For comparison, the differences between the MicroCATs temperatures are also shown in the lower panel.

Temperature differences between the 125-m ADCP and the temperatures from adjacent MicroCATs at 120 and 135-m during WHOTS-19 are shown in Fig. 5.6. The three WHOTS-19 panels reveal that temperature differences between the 125 m ADCP and the flanking 120 m and 135 m MicroCATs remain centered near 0°C for most of the record, indicating the ADCP thermometer tracks the dedicated sensors well; large positive excursions ($\sim 2\text{--}3^{\circ}\text{C}$) in late December 2023 - January 2024—and matching spikes in the MicroCAT-to-MicroCAT gradient—show that those brief anomalies arise from real, steep stratification at the thermocline’s upper edge rather than sensor drift. Seasonal trends are also clear: the vertical gradient gradually intensifies from summer to mid-winter, peaks during the January event, then collapses after March as mixing deepens the surface layer.

5.1.4 Conductivity Calibration

The results of the Sea-Bird post-recovery conductivity calibrations indicated that some MicroCAT conductivity sensors experienced relatively large offsets from their pre-deployment calibration. These were qualitatively confirmed by comparing the mooring data against CTD data from casts conducted between 200 m and 5 km from the mooring during HOT cruises. The conductivity offsets are not apparent, and there may have been multiple causes (see [Freitag *et al.*, 1999] for a similar experience with conductivity cells during COARE). For some instruments, the offset was negative, caused perhaps by biofouling of the conductivity cell. In contrast, for others, the offset was positive, for reasons still unknown. A visual inspection of the instruments after recovery did not show any apparent signs of biofouling. There were no cell scourings reported in the post-recovery reviews at Sea-Bird.

Corrections of the MicroCATs conductivity data were conducted by comparing them against CTD data from profiles and yo-yo casts conducted near the mooring during HOT cruises and during deployment/recovery cruises. Casts led between 200 and 1000 m from the mooring were given extra weight in the correction compared to those conducted between 1 and 5 km away. Casts more than 5 km away from the mooring were not used. Given that the CTD casts are conducted at least 200 m from the mooring, CTD and MicroCAT data’s alignment was done in density rather than in-depth. For cases where the alignment in density was not possible due to large conductivity offsets (causing unrealistic mooring density values), the alignment was done in temperature space. A cubic least-squares fit (LSF) to the CTD-MicroCAT differences against time was applied as a first approximation, and the corresponding correction was applied.

Some sensors had large offsets and noticeable variability that could not be explained by a cubic LSF (see below). For these sensors, a stepwise correction was applied to match the data to the available CTD cast data and then to use the differences between consecutive sensors to determine when the sensor started to drift. For instance, during periods of weak stratification, the conductivity difference between neighboring sensors A, B, and C could reach near-zero values, in particular for instruments near the surface, which are the ones most prone to suffer conductivity offsets. A sudden conductivity offset observed during this period between sensors A and B, but not between sensors A and C could indicate the beginning of an offset for sensor B.

Given that the most in-depth instruments on the mooring are less likely to be affected by biofouling and consequent sudden conductivity drift, the deep instruments served as an excellent reference to find any possible malfunction in the shallower ones. Therefore, the conductivity from the deepest instruments was corrected first, and the correction was continued sequentially upwards toward the shallower ones.

Fig. 5.3: The temperature difference between the 7-m MicroCAT and the 10-m VMCM (upper pane); between the 15-m MicroCAT and the 10-m VMCM (middle panel); and between the 7-m and the 15-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-19 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.

Fig. 5.4: The temperature difference between the 25-m MicroCAT and the 30-m VMCM (upper panel); between the 35-m MicroCAT and the 30-m VMCM (middle panel); and between the 25-m and the 35-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-19 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.

Fig. 5.5: The temperature difference between the 45-m MicroCAT and the 47.5-m ADCP (upper panel). (The ADCP stopped collecting data on 2024/3/25); between the 50-m MicroCAT and the 47.5-m ADCP (middle panel); and between the 45-m and the 50-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-19 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.

Fig. 5.6: The temperature difference between the 120-m MicroCAT and the 125-m ADCP (upper panel); between the 135-m MicroCAT and the 125-m ADCP (middle panel); and between the 120-m and the 135-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-19 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.

As a quality control to the conductivity corrections, the buoyancy frequency between neighboring instruments was calculated using finite differences. Over- or under-corrected conductivities yielded instabilities in the water column (negative buoyancy frequency) that were easy to detect and were not real when lasting for several days. Based on this, the conductivity correction of the corresponding sensors was revised.

Correction of the deep and the near-bottom MicroCATs' conductivities were done following similar procedures than for the shallow instruments, by comparing them against CTD data from near-bottom profiles conducted during HOT cruises (Fig. 5.7, bottom panel). After correction, the salinity differences between both instruments were in the ± 0.001 range.

Another characteristic of the offsets in the conductivity sensors is that their development is not always linear in time. Their behavior can be highly variable [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007]. The corrections applied to each of the conductivity sensors during WHOTS-19 are shown in Fig. 5.8 through Fig. 5.14. Most of the instruments had a drift of less than 0.02 Siemens/m for the duration of the deployment, corrected with a linear, cubic least-squares or stepwise fit.

5.2 Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler

Two TRDI broadband Workhorse Sentinel ADCP's were deployed on the WHOTS-19 mooring. A 600 kHz ADCP was deployed at 47.5 m depth in the upward-looking configuration, and a 300 kHz ADCP was deployed at 125 m, also in the upward-looking configuration. The instruments were installed in aluminum frames and an external battery module to provide sufficient power for the intended period of deployment. The four ADCP beams were angled at 20° from the vertical line of the instrument. The 300 kHz ADCP was set to profile across 30 range cells of 4 m with the first bin centered at 6.21m from the transducer. The 600 kHz ADCP was set to profile across 25 range cells of 4 m with the first bin centered at 3.10m from the transducer. The specifications of the instrument are shown in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3: Specifications of the ADCP's used for the WHOTS-19 mooring.

Frequency (kHz)	Instrument	Model	Serial Number
300	TRDI Workhorse Sentinel	WHS300-I-UG-129	7637
600	TRDI Workhorse Sentinel	WHS600-I	13917

5.2.1 Compass Calibrations

5.2.1.1 Pre-Deployment

Before the WHOTS-19 deployment, field calibration of the internal ADCPs compass was performed at the University of Hawaii's at Manoa on May 2023, for 300 kHz and the 600 kHz instruments. Each instrument was mounted in the deployment cage with the external battery module in an area located away from potential sources of magnetic field disturbances. The ADCP was mounted to a turntable, aligned with the magnetic north using a surveyor's compass. Using the built-in RDI calibration procedure, the instrument was tilted in one direction between 10 and 20 degrees and then rotated through 360 degrees at less than 5° per second. The ADCP was then tilted in a different direction, and a second rotation was made. Based on the results from the first two rotations, calibration parameters are temporarily loaded, and the instrument, tilted in a third direction, is rotated once more to check the calibration. Results from each pre-deployment field calibration are shown in Table 5.4 and Table 5.5 (Fig. 5.15 and Fig. 5.16).

Fig. 5.7: Temperature differences (top panel) and salinity differences (bottom panel) between MicroCATs #11380 and #11381 during WHOTS-19. The blue (red) lines are the differences before (after) correcting the data following the text's procedures.

Fig. 5.8: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 1 to 7 meters during WHOTS-19.

Fig. 5.9: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 15 to 35 meters during WHOTS-19

Fig. 5.10: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 40 to 50 meters during WHOTS-19

Fig. 5.11: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 55 to 75 meters during WHOTS-19.

Fig. 5.12: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 85 to 105 meters during WHOTS-19.

Fig. 5.13: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 120 to 155 meters during WHOTS-19

Fig. 5.14: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs at 4665 meters during WHOTS-19.

Table 5.4: Results from the WHOTS-19 pre-deployment 300 kHz ADCP compass field calibration procedure. *SCE* = *Single Cycle Error* (°); *DCE* = *Double Cycle Error* (°); *LD_SCE* = *Largest Double + Single Cycle Error* (°); *RMS_RE* = *RMS of 3rd Order and Higher + Random Error* (°); *OE* = *Overall Error* (°); *PM_STD* = *Pitch, Mean and St. Deviation* (°); *RM_STD* = *Roll, Mean and St. Dev.* (°)

(SN 7637)	SCE	DCE	LD_SCE	RMS_RE	OE	PM_STD	RM_STD
Before	3.74	0.02	3.77	0.10	3.74	17.71 ± 0.60	0.09 ± 0.55
After	0.44	0.34	0.78	0.14	0.64	-16.19 ± 0.59	0.00 ± 0.56

Table 5.5: Results from the WHOTS-19 pre-deployment 600 kHz ADCP compass field calibration procedure. See acronyms on Table 5.4

(SN 13917)	SCE	DCE	LD_SCE	RMS_RE	OE	PM_STD	RM_STD
Before	4.42	0.45	4.88	0.09	4.45	1.55 ± 0.59	0.21 ± 0.55
After	0.22	0.13	0.34	0.09	0.29	-15.77 ± 0.61	0.01 ± 0.57

5.2.1.2 Post-Deployment

After the WHOTS-19 mooring was recovered, the ADCP compass's performance was tested at the University of Hawai'i's at Manoa on June 13, 2024, with an identical compass calibration procedure as during the pre-deployment calibration. Results from the WHOTS-19 post-deployment ADCP compass field calibration procedure are listed in Table 5.6 and Table 5.7 (Fig. 5.15 and Fig. 5.16).

Table 5.6: Results from the WHOTS-19 post-deployment 300kHz ADCP compass field calibration procedure. See acronyms on Table 5.4

(SN 4891)	SCE	DCE	LD_SCE	RMS_RE	OE	PM_STD	RM_STD
After	2.49	0.12	2.61	0.09	2.50	1.56 ± 0.53	-0.01 ± 0.47

Table 5.7: Results from the WHOTS-19 post-deployment 600kHz ADCP compass field calibration procedure. See acronyms on Table 5.4

(SN 1825)	SCE	DCE	LD_SCE	RMS_RE	OE	PM_STD	RM_STD
After	0.99	0.08	1.07	0.15	0.99	1.61 ± 0.58	0.32 ± 0.52

5.2.2 ADCP Configurations

Individual configurations for the two ADCP's on the WHOTS-19 mooring are detailed in [WHOTS-19 300 kHz - Serial 7367](#), and [WHOTS-19 600 kHz - Serial 13917](#). The salient differences for each of the ADCP's are summarized below.

Fig. 5.15: Results of the post-cruise compass calibration, conducted June 13, 2024, on ADCP SN 7637 at the University of Hawai'i at Manoa.

Fig. 5.16: Results of the post-cruise compass calibration, conducted June 13, 2024, on ADCP SN 13917 at the University of Hawai'i at Manoa.

5.2.2.1 300 kHz (SN/7367 - 125m)

The ADCP, set to a beam frequency of 300 kHz, was configured in a burst sampling mode consisting of 40 pings per ensemble to resolve low-frequency wave orbital motions. The interval between each ping was 4 seconds, so the ensemble length was 160 seconds. The interval between ensembles was 10 minutes. Data were recorded in earth coordinates, with a heading bias of 9.34° E due to magnetic declination. False targets, usually fish, were screened by setting the threshold maximum to 70 counts. Velocity data were rejected if the difference in echo intensity among the four beams exceeded this threshold.

5.2.2.2 600 kHz (SN/13917- 47.5m)

The ADCP, set to a beam frequency of 600 kHz, was configured in a burst sampling mode consisting of 80 pings per ensemble. The interval between each ping was 2 seconds, so the ensemble length was also 160 seconds. The interval between ensembles was 10 minutes. Data were recorded in earth coordinates with a heading bias of 9.34° E. The threshold maximum was also set to 70 counts. Velocity data were rejected if the difference in echo intensity among the four beams exceeded this threshold.

5.2.3 ADCP data processing procedures

Binary files output from the ADCP were read and converted to MATLAB™ binary files using scripts developed by [Eric Firing's ADCP lab](#). The beginning of the raw data files was truncated to a time after the mooring anchor was released to allow time for the anchor to reach the seabed and for the mooring motions that follow the anchor's impact on the seafloor to dissipate. The pitch, roll, and ADCP temperature were examined to pick reasonable times that ensured good data quality without unnecessarily discarding too much data ([Fig. 5.17](#), [Fig. 5.18](#)). Truncation at the end of the data files was chosen to be the ensemble before the acoustic release signal was sent to avoid contamination due to the instrument's ascent. The times of the first ensemble from the raw data, deployments, and recovery time, along with the truncated records of both deployments, are shown in [Table 5.8](#).

Table 5.8: ADCP record times (UTC mm/dd/yyyy, hh:mm:ss) for WHOTS-19.

Activities	300 kHz	600 kHz
Raw file start	06/15/2023, 23:59:00	06/15/2023, 23:59:00
Raw file end	06/07/2024, 18:48:59	03/25/2024, 15:38:59
ADCP In water	06/16/2023, 21:47:00	06/16/2023, 21:23:00
Anchor over	06/17/2023, 02:59:00	06/17/2023, 02:59:00
Anchor release fired	06/06/2024, 18:00:00	06/06/2024, 18:00:00
ADCP on deck	06/07/2024, 00:17:00	06/07/2024, 00:29:00

5.2.3.1 ADCP Clock Drift

Upon recovery, a spike is normally produced in the ADCP data by gently rubbing each instrument's transducer by hand for 20 seconds (see [Table 3.7](#)) to compare the ADCP clocks with the ship's time server. Past deployments of the ADCP's suggest a 3-minute difference on ADCP clocks is not unusual. No drift corrections were made. However, this drift may be significant if the data are used for time-dependent analysis, such as tidal or spectrum analysis. A drift correction needs to be applied in those cases.

Fig. 5.17: Temperature record from the 300 kHz ADCP during WHOTS-19 mooring (top panel). The bottom panel shows the beginning and end of the record, with the green vertical line representing the in-water time during deployment and out-of-water recovery time. The red line represents the anchor release and acoustic release trigger for deployment and recovery, respectively.

Fig. 5.18: Same as Fig. 5.17, but for the 600 kHz ADCP.

5.2.3.2 Heading Bias

As mentioned in the ADCP configuration section, the data were recorded in the earth coordinates. A heading bias, the angle between magnetic north and true north, can be included in the setup to obtain output data in true-earth coordinates. Magnetic variation was obtained from the [National Geophysical Data Center ‘Geomag’ calculator](#). A constant value is acceptable for a yearlong deployment because the change in declination is small, approximately $-0.02^{\circ}\text{year}^{-1}$ at the WHOTS location. A heading bias of 9.34° was entered in the setup of the WHOTS-19 ADCP’s.

5.2.3.3 Quality Control

Quality control of the ADCP data involved the thorough examination of the velocity, instrument orientation, and diagnostic fields to develop the basis of the QC flagging procedures. Details of the methods used can be found in the WHOTS Data Report 1 [[Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007](#)]. The following QC procedures were applied to the WHOTS-19 deployment of ADCP data.

1. The first bin (closest to the transducer) is sometimes corrupted due to what is known as ringing. A period of time is needed for the sound energy produced during a transducer’s transmit pulse to dissipate before the ADCP can adequately receive the returned echoes. This “blanking interval” is used to prevent useless data from being recorded. If it is too short, signal returns can be contaminated by the lingering noise from the transducer. The blanking interval is expressed as a distance. The default value of 1.76 m was used for the 300 kHz ADCP, whereas an interval of 0.88 m was used for the 600 kHz ADCP. As a result, bin one was flagged and replaced with Not a Number (NaN) in the quality-controlled dataset ([Fig. 5.19](#)).

Fig. 5.19: Eastward velocity component for the 300 kHz (top panel) and the 600 kHz (bottom panel) ADCPs are showing the incoherence between depth bins 1 (red), 2 (green), and 3 (blue).

2. For an upward-looking ADCP with a beam angle of 20° within range of the sea surface, the upper 6% of the depth range is contaminated with sidelobe interference [Teledyne RD Instruments, 2011]. This contamination results from the much stronger signal reflection from the sea surface than from scatters, overwhelming the sidelobe suppression of the transducer. Data quality is quantified using echo intensity, a measure of the backscattered echo's strength for each depth cell. With distance from the transducer sensor, echo intensity is expected to decrease. Sharp increases in echo intensity indicate contamination from surface reflection. Most of the data within the upper four bins ($\sim 14\%$ of the vertical range) were flagged. These top four bins range from about 15 m up to the sea surface.
3. The use of four beams (along with instrument orientation) is used to resolve currents into their component earth-referenced velocities, providing a second estimate of the vertical velocity. The scaled difference between these estimates is defined as the error velocity, and it is useful for assessing data quality. Error velocities with an absolute magnitude more significant than 0.15ms^{-1} (value comparable to the standard deviation of observed horizontal velocities) were flagged and removed.
4. An indication of data quality for each ensemble is given by the "percent good" data indicator, which accompanies each beam for each bin. The use of the percent good indicator is determined by the coordinate transformation mode used during the data collection. For profiles transformed into earth coordinates, the percent good field shows the percentage of pings that could be used to create the earth coordinate velocities. The percent good fields show the percentage of data made using 4 and 3 beam solutions in each depth cell within an ensemble and the percentage that was rejected due to failing one of the criteria set during the instrument setup (see *WHOTS-19 300 kHz - Serial 7367*). Data were flagged when data in each depth cell within an ensemble made from 3 or 4 beam solutions was 20% or less.
5. Data were rejected using correlation magnitude, which is the pulse-to-pulse correlation (in ping returns) for each depth cell. Correlation magnitude represents how the shape of the received signal corresponds to the outgoing signal for each ping. If at least three of the beams exhibited a correlation magnitude more significant than 64 counts for a given bin, the profile could be transformed into earth coordinates. Low correlation magnitudes may indicate sudden changes in particle density or sudden changes in ADCP tilt. More research is needed at this time into relationships between ADCP tilt and correlation magnitude. If any beam had a correlation magnitude of 20 counts or less, that data point was flagged.
6. Histograms of raw vertical velocity data and partially cleaned data from the ADCP (Fig. 5.20 and Fig. 5.21) and the WHOTS Data Report 1 [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007] showed vertical velocities larger than expected, some exceeding 1ms^{-1} . Recall that the instruments' burst sampling (4-second intervals for the 300 kHz and 2-second intervals for the 600 kHz, for 160 seconds every 10 minutes) was designed to minimize aliasing by occasional large ocean swell orbital motions *Description of WHOTS-19 Mooring*, and therefore are not the source of these speeds in the data. These significant vertical speeds are possibly fish swimming in the beams based on the histograms of the partially cleaned data; depth cells with an absolute value of vertical velocity greater than 0.3ms^{-1} were flagged.
7. A quality control routine known as 'edgers' identifies outliers in surface bins using a five-point median differencing method. The median velocity from surface bins was calculated for each ensemble, and then a five-point running median of the surface bin median was calculated. This last median was then compared to individual velocity observations in the surface bins, and those differing by greater than 0.48ms^{-1} were flagged.
8. A 5-pole low pass Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of $0.25\frac{\text{cycles}}{\text{hour}}$ was used upon the time-series' length to isolate low-frequency flow for each bin independently. The low-frequency flow is then subtracted, giving a time series of high-frequency velocity component fluctuations for each bin. Data points were considered outliers when their values exceeded four standard deviations from the mean (for each bin) and were removed.
9. A median residual filter used a 7-point (70 minutes) median differencing method to define velocity fluctuations. A 7-point running median is calculated for each bin independently, and the result is subtracted out, giving time series of variations relative to the running median. Outliers higher than four standard deviations from the mean of the 7 points are flagged and removed for each bin.
10. Meticulous verification of all the quality control routines was performed through visual inspections of the quality-controlled velocity data. Two methods were utilized; time-series of u and v components for multiple bins were evaluated, and individual vertical profiles. The time-series methodology involved inspecting u and v components separately, five bins at a time, over 600 ensembles (100 hours). Any instance showing one bin behaving erratically from the other four bins was investigated further. If it seemed that there could be no reasonable rationale for the erratic points from the identified bin, the points were flagged. The intent of the inspection of vertical profiles of u and v components was to find entire profiles that were not aligned with neighboring profiles. Thirty u and v profiles were stacked at a time and were visually inspected for any anomalous data.

Fig. 5.20: Histogram of the vertical velocity of the 300 kHz ADCP for raw data (top panel) and enlarged for clarity (upper middle panel), and partial quality controlled data (lower middle panel) and enlarged for clarity (bottom).

Fig. 5.21: Same as Fig. 5.20, but for 600kHz ADCP.

5.3 Vector Measuring Current Meter (VMCM)

Vector measuring current meters (VMCM) were deployed on the WHOTS-19 mooring at depths of 10 m and 30 m, serial numbers SN 0035 and 0058, respectively. VMCM data were processed by the WHOI/UOP group, and the record times are shown in [Table 5.9](#).

Table 5.9: Record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm) for the VMCMs at 10 m and 30 m during the WHOTS-19 deployment

Time Over	VMCM (SN 0035)	VMCM (SN 0058)
Deployment	06/16/23 20:28	06/16/23 20:16
Recovery	06/07/24 01:47	06/07/24 02:01

Daily (24 hours) moving averages of quality controlled 600 kHz ADCP data are compared to VMCM data interpolated to the ADCP ensemble times in the top panels of [Fig. 5.22](#) through [Fig. 5.25](#), and the difference is shown in the middle panels. The absolute value of the mean difference plus or minus one standard deviation is shown at the top of the middle panel. Velocities are not compared if greater than 80% of the ADCP data within a 24-hour average was flagged. The absolute value of mean differences for all deployments and both velocity components varied between 3 and 4 cms^{-1} , with standard deviations between 2.9 and 3.2 cms^{-1} . The VMCM data does not appear to degrade over time for any deployment. Propeller fouling would dampen measured VMCM velocity magnitudes, but a decrease in VMCM velocity magnitude than ADCP velocity magnitude with time is not observed.

5.4 Global Positioning System Receiver

Xeos Global Positioning System receiver (Melo-IMEI:300034013707580) and (Rover-IMEI:300434063547190) were attached to the buoy's tower top during the WHOTS-19 deployment ([Description of WHOTS-19 Mooring](#)). Data returns from the receiver were high ([Table 5.10](#)).

Table 5.10: GPS record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm) during WHOTS-19

Raw file	Xeos GPS (Melo)	Xeos GPS (Rover)
Start Time	06/17/23 17:03	04/10/23 19:12
End Time	06/07/24 23:53	06/09/24 00:40

Fig. 5.22: A comparison of 30 m VMCM and ADCP U velocity for WHOTS-19. The top panel shows 24-hour moving averages of VMCM zonal (U) velocity at 30 m depth (red) and ADCP U velocity from the nearest depth bin to 30 m (30.22 m). The middle panel shows the U velocity difference, and the bottom panel shows the percentage of ADCP data within the moving average not flagged by quality control methods.

Fig. 5.23: Same as in Fig. 5.22 but for the meridional (V) velocity component.

Fig. 5.24: Same as in Fig. 5.22 but for the 10 m VMCM.

Fig. 5.25: Same as Fig. 5.24, but for the meridional (V) velocity component.

During the WHOTS-19 mooring deployment on 17 June 2023, synoptic charts showed a pronounced high-pressure ridge to the north of the Hawaiian Islands. The resulting pressure gradient sustained moderate easterly trade winds that strengthened slightly over the course of the cruise, averaging 15–16 kt during the deployment window. Skies remained clear, no measurable precipitation was recorded, and only small short-period wind waves were observed. Surface current measurements indicated a westward flow of approximately 0.5 kt. Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) data revealed a predominantly northwestward current throughout the upper 200 m, consistent with an elevated sea-surface height field north of Station ALOHA. Superimposed upon this background flow were strong semidiurnal and diurnal internal tides and near-inertial oscillations, producing pronounced vertical shear. Hydrographic profiles collected near the WHOTS-18 buoy (Station 52) (Fig. 6.1–Fig. 6.3) documented a mixed layer roughly 40 dbar deep and a subsurface salinity maximum centred between 130 dbar and 150 dbar. CTD casts near the WHOTS-19 buoy (Station 50) were aborted following *CTD modulo* errors that indicated intermittent deck-unit communication problems.

Conditions during the subsequent WHOTS-19 recovery and WHOTS-20 deployment on 16 June 2024 were more energetic. The same high-pressure ridge persisted, but trade-wind speeds peaked near 22 kt at the start of operations before easing to about 7 kt by cruise end; clear skies again prevailed and no rainfall was recorded. A 1.5–2 m swell propagated from the north-northwest. Near-surface currents reached almost 1 kt toward the north-northwest, and ADCP observations showed this flow extending through at least the upper 300 m, once more coincident with elevated sea level north of the mooring. Internal semidiurnal and diurnal tidal constituents, together with near-inertial motions, generated substantial vertical shear throughout the upper-ocean velocity field. Pre-recovery CTD casts adjacent to the WHOTS-19 buoy (Station 50) (Fig. 6.4– Fig. 6.6) recorded a slightly deeper mixed layer of roughly 50 dbar and a sharper, shallower subsurface salinity maximum near 60 dbar. CTD casts were also performed near the WHOTS-20 buoy (Station 52) (Fig. 6.7–Fig. 6.8)

Hourly temperature and salinity from the sixteen MicroCAT recorders (sampling depths 1.5–155 m) reveal a coherent seasonal thermohaline signal modulated by two prominent anomalies. In the upper 25 m the mixed-layer temperature increased quasi-linearly from 25 °C in June 2023 to a late-October maximum of 27.2 °C, then decreased at roughly 0.06 °Cd⁻¹ to a February–March 2024 minimum of 23 °C, recovering to ~24 °C by June 2024 (Fig. 6.13). The amplitude of this seasonal cycle attenuates with depth—from 3.4 °C at 40 m to 1.4 °C at 155 m—and the timing of extrema lags downward at an average phase speed of 3 md⁻¹, indicating vertical propagation of the annual harmonic and intermittent mixing events (Fig. 6.14, Fig. 6.15, Fig. 6.16).

Salinity lacks a simple annual cycle but is dominated by two events centered between 40 m and 85 m (Fig. 6.18, Fig. 6.19). First, from August to November 2023 a high-salinity intrusion raised values by 0.30–0.45 to a peak of 35.35, with only weak expression in the surface layer and little signal below 120 m. The vertical structure and timing suggest lateral advection of the subtropical surface-salinity maximum followed by subduction into the upper pycnocline. Second, in May 2024 all instruments above 25 m registered a rapid freshening to 34.7–34.8, while the 75 m sensor fell by <0.05. Although no concurrent meteorological record is available to attribute a single cause, the timing and shallow vertical extent imply an episodic surface-buoyancy input—most likely a combination of rainfall and diminished wind mixing. Superimposed on these large-scale anomalies are shorter (2–4 d) fresh pulses in July 2023 and February 2024 that penetrated to ~95 m, probably arising from convective overturning during brief trade-wind relaxations.

Taken together, the late-summer temperature maximum coupled with a salinity increase, followed by winter cooling and a spring freshening, underscores the seasonal interplay between local buoyancy forcing and mesoscale advection near Station ALOHA. Below 120 m both variables remain comparatively steady, confirming that the MicroCAT array spans the actively ventilated layer yet resides above the potential-density surface $\sigma_\theta \approx 26.4$ that caps intermediate-water formation in the central North Pacific.

Figures Fig. 6.25–Fig. 6.27 synthesize twenty years of WHOTS SeaCAT/MicroCAT observations into depth–time and density frameworks that together delineate the evolving thermohaline structure of the upper 150 m at Station ALOHA. The temperature section (upper panel of Fig. 6.25) exhibits a robust seasonal cycle: near-surface waters warm to 26–28 °C every boreal summer and cool to 18–22 °C each winter, the annual amplitude diminishing below 120 m. In contrast, the salinity section (lower panel of Fig. 6.25) is dominated by multi-year modulation of the subsurface salinity maximum centred between 40 m and 90 m. Salinity hovered near 34.8–35.0 g kg⁻¹ from 2005 to 2008, increased episodically to 35.4 g kg⁻¹ during 2009–2015, declined sharply to minima of 34.4 g kg⁻¹ in 2019–2020, and rebounded above 35.3 g kg⁻¹ after 2021, occasionally shoaling to the upper 20 m in late 2022. When replotted in density space (Fig. 6.27) these excursions collapse onto a narrow isopycnal envelope, with the salinity maximum persistently occupying $\sigma_\theta = 24.5$ kg m⁻³ and the salinity minimum constrained by $\sigma_\theta = 25.0$ kg m⁻³. The fact that warm–fresh and cool–salty anomalies manifest primarily as vertical displacements of isopycnals, rather than changes in their absolute value, indicates a tight thermohaline compensation that maintains nearly constant density—a signature of mode-water formation and lateral subduction in the subtropical gyre. Although alternating high- and low-salinity phases punctuate the record, the combined panels reveal no monotonic trend in either temperature or salinity over the 2004–2024 interval.

The near-bottom record (4665 m) from the two WHOTS-19 MicroCATs tracks the abyssal variability observed 74 m deeper at the ALOHA Cabled Observatory (ACO; 4739 m) with remarkable fidelity in both potential temperature and salinity (Fig. 6.28). From June to mid-November 2023 potential temperature climbed gradually from 1.110 °C to 1.116 °C, after which three discrete cooling events are evident: a sharp drop of 0.008 °C in mid-December, a briefer decrease of 0.004 °C in early February, and a smaller excursion in late May 2024. Each temperature minimum recorded by the MicroCAT pair is mirrored—within measurement noise—by the daily-averaged ACO series, indicating that the signals represent regional abyssal water-mass intrusions rather than mooring-specific artifacts.

Salinity exhibits synchronous structure on the order of 10⁻³ g kg⁻¹. A slow freshening of 0.001 g kg⁻¹ spans June–December 2023, followed by episodic salinity increases that coincide with the December, February, and May cold pulses, and a return toward the June baseline by the end of the record. The consistent phase relationship—cooler water arriving with slightly higher salinity—supports the interpretation of these features as propagating deep-water anomalies previously documented at Station ALOHA [Lukas *et al.*, 2001], now routinely monitored by ACO instrumentation [Howe *et al.*, 2011]. The close correspondence between the WHOTS MicroCATs and the ACO series demonstrates that the WHOTS mooring, although ~6 nmi to the south, resolves the same abyssal variability and thus provides a reliable, independent measure of deep-water changes in the region.

Fig. 6.31 through Fig. 6.33 shows the time series of the zonal, meridional, and vertical currents recorded with the moored ADCPs during the WHOTS-19 deployment. Fig. 6.29 presents a two-decade perspective (WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-19) on the zonal (u), meridional (v), and vertical (w) velocity fields measured by the mooring-mounted ADCPs. Despite several multi-month data gaps—most noticeably between late 2008 and early 2010—the zonal and meridional sections reveal pronounced mesoscale variability. Alternating bands of eastward (red) and westward (blue) flow, and their north-/south-flow counterparts, coincide with the passage of anticyclonic and cyclonic eddies that regularly cross Station ALOHA. Superimposed on this eddy background are shorter episodes of persistent flow anomalies; the energetic eastward burst during 2007–2008 is a prominent example. The vertical-velocity panel highlights a transition in signal amplitude near 47 m. Above this depth the 600 kHz ADCP (mounted at 47.5 m) records comparatively small vertical excursions, whereas below 50 m the 300 kHz instrument (mounted at 126 m) registers larger upward and downward motions—consistent with greater tilt of the deeper instrument and the larger orbital displacements induced by surface swell at that depth.

A direct mooring–shipboard comparison was impossible during the WHOTS-19 recovery cruise because CTD casts at the buoy were aborted after module errors; the first post-redeployment check therefore came on the WHOTS-20 deployment cruise, where the zonal and meridional velocity sections from the OS75 shipboard ADCP and the co-located WH-300 moored ADCP (see Fig. 6.34 and Fig. 6.35) show nearly identical alternating flows throughout 30–130 m, with typical differences < 0.05 m s⁻¹ and small phase shifts that reflect the ~3–4 km ship-to-buoy separation and unfiltered mooring knock-down; discrepancies are largest in the wave-affected upper 15–20 m and below ~100 m where signal-to-noise declines. Complementary profile-by-profile comparisons for the five HOT cruises (HOT-343 – 347) in Fig. 6.36 – Fig. 6.37 confirm this performance: across both the 300 kHz and 600 kHz

moored instruments, biases generally remain within $\pm 0.03\text{--}0.07\text{ m s}^{-1}$, reinforcing that the WHOTS-20 velocity array is operating well within expected uncertainty bounds.

Fig. 6.39 shows the WHOTS-19 buoy meandering within roughly $\pm 0.05^\circ$ (5 km) of its nominal anchor point at $22^\circ 46.002\text{ N}$, $157^\circ 53.768\text{ W}$. High-frequency wiggles—most evident as closely spaced oscillations through the record—reflect diurnal (K1) and semidiurnal (M2) tidal forcing, while broader excursions in November 2023 and February–April 2024 are consistent with episodic eddy advection. Periods when the buoy drifts farthest from the anchor coincide with larger ADCP tilt values (Fig. 6.41), as the mooring line steepens when the surface package is displaced, confirming the expected coupling between horizontal offset and instrument inclination.

6.1 CTD Profiling Data

Profiles of temperature, salinity, and potential density ($\sigma\theta$) from the casts obtained during the WHOTS-19 deployment cruise are presented in Fig. 6.1 through Fig. 6.4, together with the results of bottle determination of salinity. Fig. 6.4 through Fig. 6.8 shows the results of the CTD profiles during the WHOTS-20 cruise.

6.2 Thermosalinograph Data

Underway measurements of near-surface temperature and salinity from the thermosalinograph (TSG) system on board the R/V Oscar Sette cruise are presented in Fig. 6.9 and navigational data is shown in Fig. 6.10 for the WHOTS-19 cruise. TSG and navigational data during the WHOTS-20 cruise, on board the R/V Oscar Sette, are presented in Fig. 6.11 and Fig. 6.12, respectively. Note that the WHOTS-20 displayed temperature is from the internal TSG sensor, and it does not represent the near-surface temperature. The remote temperature sensor on the ship Oscar Elton Sette was not functional during this cruise.

6.3 MicroCAT Data

The temperatures measured by MicroCATs during the mooring deployment for WHOTS-19 are presented in Fig. 6.13 through Fig. 6.16 for each of the depths where the instruments were located. The salinities are plotted in Fig. 6.17 through Fig. 6.20. The potential densities ($\sigma\theta$) are plotted in Fig. 6.21 through Fig. 6.24.

Contoured plots of temperature and salinity as a function of depth for the deployments WHOTS-1 through -19 are presented in Fig. 6.25, and contoured plots of potential density ($\sigma\theta$) as a function of depth are in Fig. 6.26, and of salinity as a function of $\sigma\theta$ are in Fig. 6.27.

The potential temperature (θ) and salinity measured by the deep MicroCATs during the mooring deployment are shown in Fig. 6.28. Also shown in the plot are the θ and salinity data obtained with a MicroCAT (SBE-37) installed in the ALOHA Cabled Observatory, about six nautical miles north from the WHOTS-19 anchor. The instrument is located 2 m above the bottom.

6.4 Moored ADCP Data

6.4.1 Long-term variability

The velocity climatology in Fig. 6.29 spans nearly two decades of WHOTS moorings. Alternating eastward and westward *zonal* currents dominate the upper 60m and, during energetic intervals, penetrate to 100m. Two regime shifts are evident: (1) 2009–2011, when an instrument replacement and brief data gap coincide with a marked reduction in eastward flow; and (2) 2018 to the present, when stronger, more coherent eastward episodes re-emerge and are accompanied by enhanced downward motion below 40m.

The *meridional* record exhibits comparable inter-annual structure, with sustained northward anomalies in 2006–2007, 2013–2015, and 2020–2022, bracketed by southward phases.

Fig. 6.1: [Upper left panel] Profiles of CTD temperature, salinity, and potential density (σ_θ) as a function of pressure, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-19 cruise. [Upper right panel] Profiles of CTD salinity as a function of potential temperature, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-19 cruise. [Lower left panel] Same as in the upper left panel, but for station 52 cast 1. [Lower right panel] Same as in the upper right panel, but station 52 cast 1.

Fig. 6.2: [Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 52, cast 2. [Lower panels] Same as Fig. 6.1, but for station 52, cast 3.

Fig. 6.3: [Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 54, cast 4.

Fig. 6.4: [Upper left panel] Profiles of CTD temperature, salinity, and potential density (σ_θ) as a function of pressure, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-20 cruise. [Upper right panel] Profiles of CTD salinity as a function of potential temperature, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-20 cruise. [Lower left panel] Same as in the upper left panel, but for station 50 cast 1. [Lower right panel] Same as in the upper right panel, but station 50 cast 1.

Fig. 6.5: Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.4, but for station 50, cast 2.[Lower panels] Same as in Fig. 6.4, but for station 50, cast 3.

Fig. 6.6: Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.4, but for station 50, cast 4.[Lower panels] Same as in Fig. 6.4, but for station 50, cast 5.

Fig. 6.7: Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.4, but for station 52, cast 1. [Lower panels] Same as in Fig. 6.4, but for station 52, cast 2.

Fig. 6.8: Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.4, but for station 52, cast 3.

Fig. 6.9: Final processed temperature (upper panel), salinity (middle panel), and potential density (σ_θ) (lower panel) data from the continuous underway system onboard the R/V Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-19 cruise. Temperature and salinity taken from 6-dbar CTD data (circles) and salinity bottle sample data (crosses) are superimposed. The dashed vertical red line indicates the period of occupation of Station ALOHA and the WHOTS site.

Fig. 6.10: Timeseries of latitude (upper panel), longitude (middle panel), and ship's speed (lower panel) during the WHOTS-19 cruise.

Fig. 6.11: Final processed temperature (upper panel), salinity (middle panel), and potential density (σ_θ) (lower panel) data from the continuous underway system onboard the R/V Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-20 cruise. The displayed temperature is from the internal TSG sensor, and it does not represent the near-surface temperature (see text). Temperature and salinity were taken from 6-dbar CTD data (circles), and salinity bottle sample data (crosses) are superimposed. The dashed vertical red line indicates the period of occupation of Station ALOHA and the WHOTS site.

Fig. 6.12: Timeseries of latitude (upper panel), longitude (middle panel), and ship's speed (lower panel) during the WHOTS-20 cruise.

Fig. 6.13: Temperatures from MicroCATs during WHOTS-19 deployment at 1.5, 7, 15, and 25 m.

Fig. 6.14: Same as in Fig. 6.13, but at 40, 45, 50, and 55 m.

Fig. 6.15: Same as in Fig. 6.13, but at 65, 75, 85, and 95 m.

Fig. 6.16: Same as in Fig. 6.13, but at 105, 120, 135, and 155 m.

Fig. 6.17: Salinities from MicroCATs during WHOTS-19 deployment at 1.5, 7, 15, and 25 m

Fig. 6.18: Same as in Fig. 6.17, but at 40, 45, 50, and 55 m.

Fig. 6.19: Same as in Fig. 6.17, but at 65, 75, 85, and 95 m

Fig. 6.20: Same as in Fig. 6.17, but at 105, 120, 135, and 155 m.

Fig. 6.21: Potential densities (σ_θ) from MicroCATs during WHOTS-19 deployment at 1.5, 7, 15, and 25 m.

Fig. 6.22: Same as in Fig. 6.21, but at 40, 45, 50, and 55 m.

Fig. 6.23: Same as in Fig. 6.21, but at 65, 75, 85, and 95 m.

Fig. 6.24: Same as in Fig. 6.21, but at 105, 120, 135, and 155 m.

FS-M 13-Feb-2025, 9:19
 /home/helu/export/aina1/whots/analysis/w1_19cont.m

Fig. 6.25: Contour plots of temperature (upper panel) and salinity (lower panel) versus depth from Seacats/MicroCATs during WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-19 deployments. The shaded areas indicate missing data. The diamonds along the right axis indicate the depths of the instrument.

FS-M 13-Feb-2025, 9:19
/home/helu/export/aina1/whots/analysis/w1_19cont.m

Fig. 6.26: Contour plots of potential density (σ_θ), versus depth from SeaCATs/MicroCATs during WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-19 deployments. The shaded areas indicate missing data. The diamonds along the right axis in the upper figure indicate the depths of the instrument.

FS-M 13-Feb-2025, 9:19
 /home/helu/export/aina1/whots/analysis/w1_19cont.m

Fig. 6.27: Contour plots of salinity versus σ_θ from SeaCATs/MicroCATs during WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-19 deployments.

Fig. 6.28: Potential temperature (upper panel) and salinity (lower panel) time-series from the ALOHA Cabled Observatory (ACO) sensors and the WHOTS-19 MicroCATs 11381 and 11380.

Vertical velocities remain an order of magnitude smaller than their horizontal counterparts ($|w| \lesssim 0.1 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), yet episodic up- and down-welling events—most frequent after 2018—highlight the influence of internal waves and shear-driven mixing.

6.4.2 WHOTS-19 deployment

The year-long WHOTS-19 record (Fig. 6.30) began with persistent westward flow (-0.10 to -0.25 m s^{-1}) that lasted until early November 2023. A basin-scale reversal in mid-December culminated in peak eastward velocities of $+0.25 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ by mid-January. The transition back to strong westward flow (-0.50 m s^{-1}) in late February–March was followed by progressively weaker currents approaching recovery.

Meridional currents were largely northward during the first half of the deployment, interrupted by a southward pulse in August–September 2023 (-0.25 m s^{-1} between 40m and 80m). A second southward episode in March 2024 quickly gave way to vigorous northward flow of up to $+0.30 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ in April–May, consistent with the passage of mesoscale eddies through the HOT region.

Vertical motion shows coherent structure despite its small magnitude. Weak downward velocities (-0.05 m s^{-1} below 60m) accompanied the early-summer westward regime, whereas a distinct upward pulse ($+0.10 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ at 0–25m) coincided with the peak northward event in late April 2024, suggesting enhanced near-inertial energy and shear.

High-resolution staggered time series for each depth bin are provided in Fig. 6.31–Fig. 6.33; these plots retain sub-daily variability that is suppressed by the monthly contour averaging.

6.4.3 Shipboard–mooring intercomparison

During the recovery/deployment cruise the shipboard 75kHz Ocean Surveyor ADCP and the co-located 300kHz Workhorse moored ADCP sampled the same velocity field (Fig. 6.34, Fig. 6.35). Zonal currents remained uniformly westward (-0.20 to -0.50 m s^{-1}) across the 0–130m layer, while meridional flow transitioned from northward ($+0.10$ to $+0.40 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) to southward, deepening from 50m to 90m over a two-day interval. The near-identical depth–time structures testify to the fidelity of both instruments and reinforce the continuity of the WHOTS velocity time series.

No equivalent comparison is available for the WHOTS-19 cruise itself because CTD casts at Station 50 were aborted following *CTD modulo* errors that indicated intermittent deck-unit communication failures.

Comparisons between quality-controlled moored ADCPs during the WHOTS-19 deployment and available shipboard ADCP obtained during regular HOT cruises 343 to 347, and during the mooring deployment (WHOTS-19) velocity profiles were computed when HOT CTD casts were being conducted near the WHOTS mooring specifically intended to calibrate moored instrumentation (see *Conductivity Calibration*). The HOT shipboard profiles were taken when the ship was stationary, within 1 km of the mooring, and within 4 hours before the start and 4 hours after the end of the CTD cast conducted near the WHOTS mooring.

The HOT cruises conducted on the R/V Kilo Moana from HOT-343 to HOT-347 utilized various acoustic instruments for data collection. The TRDI Ocean Surveyor 38 kHz (OS38BB) was operated in broadband mode with a 12-meter bin size and 5-minute ensemble intervals, although data in broadband mode was not available for HOT-344. Additionally, the cruises used the TRDI Ocean Surveyor 38 kHz in narrowband mode (OS38NB), with a 24-meter bin size and 5-minute ensemble. Furthermore, the Teledyne Workhorse 300 kHz, with a 2-meter bin size and 2-minute ensemble intervals, was employed throughout all the cruises.

Comparisons between the 300 kHz and the shipboard ADCP were available for HOT-343 to HOT-347, as shown in (Fig. 6.36). Comparisons between the moored 600 kHz ADCP and the shipboard ADCP are presented in Fig. 6.37. Data from all other HOT cruises (348 to 350) were excluded due to a lack of comparable data.

Fig. 6.29: Depth–time contours of (top) zonal, (middle) meridional, and (bottom) vertical velocity ($m s^{-1}$) measured by moored ADCPs during WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-19 (2004–2024).

Fig. 6.30: Same as Fig. 6.29, but restricted to the WHOTS-19 deployment (June 2023 – June 2024).

Fig. 6.31: Staggered time series of zonal velocity ($m s^{-1}$) for each depth bin of the WHOTS-19 600kHz (top) and 300kHz (bottom) ADCPs. Curves are vertically offset by $0.5m s^{-1}$; bin depths are annotated at right.

Fig. 6.32: As in Fig. 6.31, but for meridional velocity.

Fig. 6.33: As in Fig. 6.31, but for vertical velocity.

6.5 Next Generation Vector Measuring Current Meter Data (VMCM)

Time-series of daily mean horizontal velocity components for the VMCM current meters deployed during WHOTS-19 at 10 m and 30 m depths are presented in Fig. 6.38. The plots show the zonal and meridional velocity components for each depth, highlighting the variability in both east-west and north-south flows.

At 10 m depth the zonal velocity begins with a pronounced westward episode of about 0.40 m s^{-1} in July–August 2023, weakens to near-zero by late autumn, then reverses to an eastward maximum of $+0.35$ to 0.40 m s^{-1} during February–March 2024 before reverting to westward flow (0.30 m s^{-1}) in April. The meridional component at the same depth is primarily northward through summer–autumn ($+0.20 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), turns southward in January–February (0.15 to 0.20 m s^{-1}), and rebounds to strong northward bursts of $+0.25$ to 0.35 m s^{-1} in April.

At 30 m depth the pattern is similar but slightly muted. Zonal speeds range from about 0.30 m s^{-1} (July–August) to $+0.35 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (February–March), implying a $\sim 15\%$ reduction in amplitude relative to 10 m. Meridional speeds vary between 0.15 m s^{-1} (early winter) and $+0.30 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (April), again mirroring the surface layer but with smoother transitions. The coherent phase evolution between 10 m and 30 m indicates that the dominant horizontal current structures span at least the upper 30 m, while the modest attenuation with depth points to shear confined largely above 40 m.

6.6 GPS Data

The GPS record (see Fig. 6.39) documents the horizontal displacement of the WHOTS-19 surface buoy relative to its charted anchor position at $22^\circ 46.002 \text{ N}$, $157^\circ 53.768 \text{ W}$. Throughout the 11-month deployment the float remained within a watch circle of 6.3 km radius, thereby satisfying the positional tolerance prescribed for WHOTS operations.

The time series is centred on 22.778° N and exhibits three episodes of enhanced meridional drift. A modest southward excursion in late August–early September 2023 was followed by the largest northward anomaly 22.832° N , or 5.5 km from the mean—between mid-October and mid-November 2023. A third interval of sustained northward displacement commenced in early February 2024 and persisted until recovery, with daily values stabilising near 22.810° N . These anomalies coincide with periods of intensified wind stress and mesoscale eddy activity identified

Fig. 6.34: Zonal velocity ($m s^{-1}$) from the shipboard 75kHz ADCP (top) and the WHOTS-19 moored 300kHz ADCP (bottom) versus depth and day-of-year during the WHOTS-19 recovery / WHOTS-20 deployment cruise. Black bars mark CTD rosette operations.

Fig. 6.35: Meridional velocity ($m s^{-1}$) from the same cruise and instruments as Fig. 6.34. Solid-dashed bars denote CTD deployment periods.

Fig. 6.36: Mean current profiles during shipboard ADCP (cyan: zonal, magenta: meridional) versus moored 300 kHz ADCP (blue: zonal, red: meridional) intercomparisons from HOTS-343 through HOTS-347. Moored minus shipboard ADCP differences shown in dotted lines (blue: zonal, red: meridional)

Fig. 6.37: Mean current profiles during shipboard ADCP (cyan: zonal, magenta: meridional) versus moored 600 kHz ADCP (blue: zonal, red: meridional) intercomparisons from HOTS-343 through HOTS-347. Moored minus shipboard ADCP differences shown in dotted lines (blue: zonal, red: meridional)

Fig. 6.38: Horizontal velocity data (ms^{-1}) during WHOTS-19 from the VMCMs at 10 m depth (first and second panel) and at 30 m depth (third and fourth panel)

in the concurrent ADCP record.

Longitudinal positions cluster about 157.900°W and range from 157.872°W to 157.950°W . The most pronounced westward shift (6.0 km) occurred on 11 January 2024, contemporaneous with the mid-winter southward latitude dip, whereas the largest eastward displacement (4.3 km) coincided with the October–November meridional peak. The close phasing between meridional and zonal anomalies indicates that the surface buoy responded coherently to the same forcing mechanisms—principally seasonal trade-wind surges and passing meso-scale eddies.

The WHOTS-19 surface float remained well within the operational watch circle, and the rapid relaxation of extreme excursions attests to the integrity of the mooring configuration under episodic atmospheric and oceanic forcing.

Fig. 6.39: GPS Latitude (upper panel) and longitude (lower panel) time series from the WHOTS-19 deployment.

Variance-preserving power spectra of the Xeos-GPS latitude and longitude series are presented in Fig. 6.40. Both spectra display a red-noise behaviour: spectral density declines quasi-monotonically from the sub-mesoscale band ($10^{-2} - 10^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) toward the inertial and tidal frequencies and reaches an instrument-noise floor of approximately $10^{-8} \text{deg}^2 \text{d}$ at frequencies $\gtrsim 4 \text{d}^{-1}$.

At sub-inertial frequencies ($f \lesssim 0.1 \text{d}^{-1}$) the latitude spectrum contains 30–40 % more variance than the longitude spectrum, reflecting the anisotropic eddy field at the WHOTS site in which north–south displacements exceed west–east motion. The spectral slope in this band is close to -2 , consistent with random-walk behaviour driven by mesoscale advection and wind forcing.

Three discrete peaks rise above the red-noise continuum:

Inertial band (0.7d^{-1}): a modest but distinct peak coincident with the local Coriolis frequency ($\phi = 22.8^\circ\text{N}$) indicates that the surface float responds to near-inertial currents generated by episodic wind events.

Diurnal tide (K1, 1.00d^{-1}): the dominant spectral line confirms that barotropic diurnal tides impart measurable

displacement to the mooring line.

Semidiurnal tide (M2, 1.93 d^{-1}): a secondary yet significant peak demonstrates that the barotropic semidiurnal signal, though weaker than K1, is also recorded by the surface float.

For frequencies above 2 d^{-1} the spectra flatten toward the noise floor, implying that high-frequency processes such as surface-wave drift contribute negligibly to net horizontal displacement. The close agreement between latitude and longitude spectra—in both peak location and continuum level—confirms that the buoy–mooring system responds isotropically to tidal and inertial forcing.

The WHOTS-19 surface-float excursions are governed primarily by sub-inertial mesoscale motions and by the K1 and M2 tidal constituents, with a secondary contribution from near-inertial oscillations. High-frequency wind-wave effects are effectively filtered by the mooring’s mechanical compliance and by the hourly GPS sampling scheme.

Fig. 6.40: The power spectrum of latitude (upper panel) and longitude (lower panel) for the WHOTS-19.

6.7 Mooring Motion

The horizontal excursion of the WHOTS-19 surface buoy, derived from the GPS record, provides a direct measure of the mooring-line deflection from vertical. Attitude sensors on the two moored ADCPs (300 kHz and 600 kHz) record the concurrent instrument tilt—the vector magnitude of pitch and roll. The relationship between these two quantities is summarised in Fig. 6.41.

Each panel presents a cloud of hourly tilt–distance pairs (blue symbols) with a quadratic least-squares fit to the median tilt computed in 0.2 km distance bins (red line). The sample size exceeds 7×10^3 for each instrument, and the Pearson correlation coefficients are $R = 0.72$ (300 kHz) and $R = 0.69$ (600 kHz), indicating a strong, statistically significant positive association.

Tilt increases systematically from 1° at minimal watch-circle radii (0.5 km) to $8\text{--}10^\circ$ when the buoy is ~ 2.3 km from the anchor. This behaviour is consistent with classical single-point mooring mechanics: larger horizontal drag on the surface float—imposed by currents, wind, and wave drift—produces greater catenary curvature and hence a steeper angle at the depth of the ADCPs. The similarity of the two fits confirms that the 300 kHz and 600 kHz instruments respond comparably to mooring-line deflection, despite their 30 m vertical separation. The maximum observed tilt (15°) remains below the manufacturer’s specification (20°), affirming that data quality was not compromised by excessive instrument attitude.

Fig. 6.41: Scatter plots of ADCP tilt and distance of the buoy to its anchor for the 300 kHz (left panel) and the 600 kHz ADCP deployments (right panel, blue circles). The red line is a quadratic fit to the median tilt calculated every 0.2 km distance bins.

Appendix: Instrument Configurations and Specifications

7.1 WHOTS-19 300 kHz - Serial 7367

```
pc1

BEAM CONTINUITY TEST

When prompted to do so, vigorously rub the selected
beam's face.

If a beam does not PASS the test, send any character to
the ADCP to automatically select the next beam.

Rub Beam 1 = PASS
Rub Beam 2 = PASS
Rub Beam 3 = PASS
Rub Beam 4 = PASS

>rr
Recorder Directory:
Volume serial number for device #0 is 1633-17f2

WHT19000 000          0 06-14-23 10:55:44p r a [ 0]

Bytes used on device #0 = 0
Volume serial number for device #1 is 3357-0de5

No files found.

Bytes used on device #1 = 0
Total capacity = 191969280 bytes
Total bytes used = 0 bytes in 1 files
Total bytes free = 191969280 bytes

>ck
[Parameters saved as USER defaults]
>deploy
Deployment Commands:
```

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(continued from previous page)

```

CF = 11101 ----- Flow Ctrl (EnsCyc;PngCyc;Binry;Ser;Rec)
CK ----- Keep Parameters as USER Defaults
CR # ----- Retrieve Parameters (0 = USER, 1 = FACTORY)
CS ----- Start Deployment

EA = +00000 ----- Heading Alignment (1/100 deg)
EB = +00934 ----- Heading Bias (1/100 deg)
ED = 01250 ----- Transducer Depth (0 - 65535 dm)
ES = 35 ----- Salinity (0-40 pp thousand)
EX = 11111 ----- Coord Transform (Xform: Type,Tilts,3 Bm,Map)
EZ = 1111101 ----- Sensor Source (C,D,H,P,R,S,T)

RE ----- Recorder ErAsE
RN ----- Set Deployment Name

TE = 00:10:00.00 ----- Time per Ensemble (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TF = 23/06/15,23:59:00 --- Time of First Ping (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TP = 00:04.00 ----- Time per Ping (min:sec.sec/100)
TS = 23/06/14,23:04:18 --- Time Set (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)

WD = 111 100 000 ----- Data Out (Vel,Cor,Amp; PG,St,P0; P1,P2,P3)
WF = 0176 ----- Blank After Transmit (cm)
Press any key to continue

WN = 030 ----- Number of depth cells (1-128)
WP = 00040 ----- Pings per Ensemble (0-16384)
WS = 0400 ----- Depth Cell Size (cm)
WV = 175 ----- Mode 1 Ambiguity Vel (cm/s radial)

>cs

```

7.2 WHOTS-19 600 kHz - Serial 13917

```

ps0
Instrument S/N: 13917
Frequency: 614400 HZ
Configuration: 4 BEAM, JANUS
Match Layer: 10
Beam Angle: 20 DEGREES
Beam Pattern: CONVEX
Orientation: UP
Sensor(s): HEADING TILT 1 TILT 2 TEMPERATURE
Temp Sens Offset: -0.03 degC

CPU Firmware: 50.40 [0]
Boot Code Ver: Required: 1.16 Actual: 1.16
DEM0D #1 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
DEM0D #2 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
PWRTIMG Ver: 85d3, Type: 6

Board Serial-Number Data:
A7 00 00 06 07 BD C0 09 PI0727-3000-00G
D3 00 00 06 07 CC 88 09 CPU727-2000-00M
8A 00 00 05 88 E4 75 09 REC727-1000-03E

```

(continues on next page)

(continued from previous page)

69 00 00 06 07 C9 BF 09 DSP727-2001-03H

ps3

Beam Width: 3.7 degrees

Beam	Elevation	Azimuth
1	-70.00	270.00
2	-70.00	90.00
3	-70.00	0.01
4	-70.00	180.00

Beam Directional Matrix (Down):

0.3420	0.0000	0.9397	0.2419
-0.3420	0.0000	0.9397	0.2419
0.0000	-0.3420	0.9397	-0.2419
0.0000	0.3420	0.9397	-0.2419

Instrument Transformation Matrix (Down) Q14:

1.4619	-1.4619	0.0000	0.0000	23952	-23952	0	0
0.0000	0.0000	-1.4619	1.4619	0	0	-23952	23952
0.2661	0.2661	0.2661	0.2661	4359	4359	4359	4359
1.0337	1.0337	-1.0337	-1.0337	16936	16936	-16936	-16936

Beam Angle Corrections Are Loaded.

pa

PREDEPLOYMENT TESTS

CPU TESTS:

RTC.....PASS
 RAM.....PASS
 ROM.....PASS

RECORDER TESTS:

PC Card #0.....*DETECTED*
 Card Detect.....PASS
 Communication.....PASS
 DOS Structure.....PASS
 Sector Test (short).....PASS
 PC Card #1.....*NOT DETECTED*

DSP TESTS:

Timing RAM.....PASS
 Demod RAM.....PASS
 Demod REG.....PASS
 FIFOs.....PASS

SYSTEM TESTS:

XILINX Interrupts... IRQ3 IRQ3 IRQ3.....PASS
 Wide Bandwidth.....PASS
 Narrow Bandwidth.....PASS
 RSSI Filter.....PASS
 Transmit.....PASS

SENSOR TESTS:

H/W Operation.....****FAIL****

pc1

BEAM CONTINUITY TEST

(Rub Beam 1-4 = PASS)

ac

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```

ACTIVE FLUXGATE CALIBRATION MATRICES in NVRAM
Calibration date and time: 5/22/1923 23:59:09
S:
  Bx  4.6233e+01  4.5450e+01  2.9114e+02  2.8383e+02
  By  1.4861e+02  5.1542e+03  5.0860e+03  5.6730e+01
  Bz  2.1848e+01  2.0786e+01  3.4930e+01  2.7030e+02
  Err 4.7694e+01  4.4911e+01  5.6584e+01  3.3404e+03
(Coils, tilt matrices, etc. omitted for brevity)

rf
RF = 31647714,223916032 --- Rec space used/free (bytes)
rs
RS = 031,213 --- Rec space used/free (MB)

rb
RECORDER TESTS: ...PASS
(running erase)
rs
RS = 000,244

rnwho19
cf11101

cs

```

7.3 WHOTS-19 MicroCAT - Headers

```

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6410
* <?xml version="1.0"?>
* <!--DeviceManager-->
* <SBEDataUploadFile>
* <ApplicationData>
* <DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.8.2</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>25-Jul-2018 07:49:42 UTC</BuildDate>
* </DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606410'>
*   <DateTime>2024-06-08T06:39:40</DateTime>
*   <DelayedStart>2023-06-06T01:00:00</DelayedStart>
*   <EventSummary numEvents='0' />
*   <Power>
*     <MainSupplyVoltage>3.64</MainSupplyVoltage>
*   </Power>
*   <ADCRatio>
*     <Ratio>7056416</Ratio>
*   </ADCRatio>
*   <Battery>
*     <Installed>2023-05-01T19:38:22</Installed>
*     <Samples>530257</Samples>
*   </Battery>
*   <MemorySummary>
*     <Samples>530257</Samples>

```

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```

*      <Bytes>2207744</Bytes>
*      <BytesFree>64376832</BytesFree>
*      </MemorySummary>
* </StatusData>
*
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606410'>
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc</Manufacturer>
*   <FirmwareVersion>SBE56 V0.98</FirmwareVersion>
*   <FirmwareDate>May 7 2019</FirmwareDate>
*   <PCBAssembly PCBID='101889' AssemblyNum='41688F' />
*   <MfgDate>Feb 25 2011</MfgDate>
*   <PCBType>0</PCBType>
*   <InternalSensors>
*     <Sensor id='Water Temperature'>
*       <type>TEMP0</type>
*       <SerialNumber>05606410</SerialNumber>
*     </Sensor>
*   </InternalSensors>
* </HardwareData>
*
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606410'>
*   <Settings
*     samplePeriod='60' format='1' />
* </ConfigurationData>
*
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606410'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMP0' id='Water Temperature'>
*     <CalDate>2023-02-18</CalDate>
*     <a0>-1.381770E-03</a0>
*     <a1>3.686239E-04</a1>
*     <a2>-7.899647E-06</a2>
*     <a3>2.292975E-07</a3>
*     <OFFSET>0.000000E+00</OFFSET>
*   </Calibration>
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
* <EventSummary DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606410'>
*   <EventList numEvents='0' maxStack='-2'>
*   </EventList>
* </EventSummary>
*
* </InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
* ** WHOTS 19 STARBOARD 240 DEG - 80 CM BELOW DECK
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 4
# nvalues = 530257
# units = specified
# name 0 = scan: Scan Count
# name 1 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 2 = t090C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C
# name 3 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 1, 530257
# span 1 = 157.041667, 525.274988

```

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```

# span 2 =      -0.0038,      34.3955
# span 3 =  0.000e+00,  0.000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jun 06 2023 01:00:00
# bad_flag =  -9.990e-29
# sensor 0 = RRatio temperature, 05606410
# datchv_date = Jun 08 2024 18:21:57, SeatermUSB v 1.8.2
# datchv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE56\SBE56_6410.xml
# datchv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6239
* <?xml version="1.0"?>
* <!--DeviceManager-->
* <SBEDataUploadFile>
* <ApplicationData>
* <DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.8.2</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>25-Jul-2018 07:49:42 UTC</BuildDate>
* </DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606239'>
*   <DateTime>2024-06-08T06:44:19</DateTime>
*   <DelayedStart>2023-06-06T01:00:00</DelayedStart>
*   <EventSummary numEvents='0' />
*   <Power>
*     <MainSupplyVoltage>3.62</MainSupplyVoltage>
*   </Power>
*   <ADCRatio>
*     <Ratio>7087738</Ratio>
*   </ADCRatio>
*   <Battery>
*     <Installed>2023-05-01T19:20:58</Installed>
*     <Samples>530263</Samples>
*   </Battery>
*   <MemorySummary>
*     <Samples>530263</Samples>
*     <Bytes>2207744</Bytes>
*     <BytesFree>64376832</BytesFree>
*   </MemorySummary>
* </StatusData>
*
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606239'>
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc</Manufacturer>
*   <FirmwareVersion>SBE56 V0.98</FirmwareVersion>
*   <FirmwareDate>May 7 2019</FirmwareDate>
*   <PCBAAssembly PCBID='101723' AssemblyNum='41688F' />
*   <MfgDate>Feb 25 2011</MfgDate>
*   <PCBType>0</PCBType>
*   <InternalSensors>
*     <Sensor id='Water Temperature'>
*       <type>TEMPO</type>
*       <SerialNumber>05606239</SerialNumber>
*     </Sensor>

```

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```

*      </InternalSensors>
*    </HardwareData>
*
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606239'>
*   <Settings
*     samplePeriod='60' format='1' />
* </ConfigurationData>
*
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606239'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMPO' id='Water Temperature'>
*     <CalDate>2023-02-18</CalDate>
*     <a0>-1.316669E-03</a0>
*     <a1>3.559913E-04</a1>
*     <a2>-7.039647E-06</a2>
*     <a3>2.108155E-07</a3>
*     <OFFSET>0.000000E+00</OFFSET>
*   </Calibration>
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
* <EventSummary DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606239'>
*   <EventList numEvents='0' maxStack='-2'>
*     </EventList>
* </EventSummary>
*
* </InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
* ** WHOTS 19 FORWARD 180 DEG - 80 CM BELOW DECK
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 4
# nvalues = 530263
# units = specified
# name 0 = scan: Scan Count
# name 1 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 2 = t090C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C
# name 3 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 1, 530263
# span 1 = 157.041667, 525.279155
# span 2 = -0.0009, 34.4112
# span 3 = 0.000e+00, 0.000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jun 06 2023 01:00:00
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# sensor 0 = RRatio temperature, 05606239
# datcnv_date = Jun 08 2024 18:21:28, SeatermUSB v 1.8.2
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE56\SBE56_6239.xml
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6412
* <?xml version="1.0"?>
* <!--DeviceManager-->
* <SBEDataUploadFile>
* <ApplicationData>

```

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```

* <DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.8.2</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>25-Jul-2018 07:49:42 UTC</BuildDate>
* </DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606412'>
*   <DateTime>2024-06-08T06:34:33</DateTime>
*   <DelayedStart>2023-06-06T01:00:00</DelayedStart>
*   <EventSummary numEvents='0' />
*   <Power>
*     <MainSupplyVoltage>3.64</MainSupplyVoltage>
*   </Power>
*   <ADCRatio>
*     <Ratio>6927505</Ratio>
*   </ADCRatio>
*   <Battery>
*     <Installed>2023-05-01T19:37:26</Installed>
*     <Samples>530252</Samples>
*   </Battery>
*   <MemorySummary>
*     <Samples>530252</Samples>
*     <Bytes>2207232</Bytes>
*     <BytesFree>64377344</BytesFree>
*   </MemorySummary>
* </StatusData>
*
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606412'>
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc</Manufacturer>
*   <FirmwareVersion>SBE56 V0.98</FirmwareVersion>
*   <FirmwareDate>May 7 2019</FirmwareDate>
*   <PCBAssembly PCBID='101848' AssemblyNum='41688F' />
*   <MfgDate>Feb 25 2011</MfgDate>
*   <PCBType>0</PCBType>
*   <InternalSensors>
*     <Sensor id='Water Temperature'>
*       <type>TEMP0</type>
*       <SerialNumber>05606412</SerialNumber>
*     </Sensor>
*   </InternalSensors>
* </HardwareData>
*
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606412'>
*   <Settings
*     samplePeriod='60' format='1' />
* </ConfigurationData>
*
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606412'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMP0' id='Water Temperature'>
*     <CalDate>2023-02-18</CalDate>
*     <a0>-1.289726E-03</a0>
*     <a1>3.514971E-04</a1>
*     <a2>-6.802816E-06</a2>
*     <a3>2.061836E-07</a3>
*     <OFFSET>0.000000E+00</OFFSET>
*   </Calibration>

```

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```

*   </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
* <EventSummary DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606412'>
*   <EventList numEvents='0' maxStack='-2'>
*     </EventList>
*   </EventSummary>
*
* </InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
* ** WHOTS 19 BOW 180 DEG - 100 CM BELOW DECK
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 4
# nvalues = 530252
# units = specified
# name 0 = scan: Scan Count
# name 1 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 2 = t090C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C
# name 3 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 1, 530252
# span 1 = 157.041667, 525.271516
# span 2 = -0.0031, 35.3966
# span 3 = 0.000e+00, 0.000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jun 06 2023 01:00:00
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# sensor 0 = RRatio temperature, 05606412
# datcnv_date = Jun 08 2024 18:22:09, SeatermUSB v 1.8.2
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE56\SBE56_6412.xml
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

```

```

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6983
* <?xml version="1.0"?>
* <!--DeviceManager-->
* <SBEDataUploadFile>
* <ApplicationData>
* <DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.8.2</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>25-Jul-2018 07:49:42 UTC</BuildDate>
* </DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606983'>
*   <DateTime>2024-06-08T06:24:52</DateTime>
*   <DelayedStart>2000-01-01T00:00:00</DelayedStart>
*   <EventSummary numEvents='0' />
*   <Power>
*     <MainSupplyVoltage>3.63</MainSupplyVoltage>
*   </Power>
*   <ADCRatio>
*     <Ratio>6837154</Ratio>
*   </ADCRatio>

```

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```

*   <Battery>
*     <Installed>2000-01-01T00:00:00</Installed>
*     <Samples>530243</Samples>
*   </Battery>
*   <MemorySummary>
*     <Samples>530243</Samples>
*     <Bytes>2207232</Bytes>
*     <BytesFree>64377344</BytesFree>
*   </MemorySummary>
* </StatusData>
*
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606983'>
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc</Manufacturer>
*   <FirmwareVersion>SBE56 V0.96</FirmwareVersion>
*   <FirmwareDate>Feb 25 2011</FirmwareDate>
*   <PCBAsembly PCBID='108806' AssemblyNum='41688F' />
*   <MfgDate>Feb 25 2011</MfgDate>
*   <PCBType>0</PCBType>
*   <InternalSensors>
*     <Sensor id='Water Temperature'>
*       <type>TEMP0</type>
*       <SerialNumber>05606983</SerialNumber>
*     </Sensor>
*   </InternalSensors>
* </HardwareData>
*
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606983'>
*   <Settings
*     samplePeriod='60' format='1' />
* </ConfigurationData>
*
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606983'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMP0' id='Water Temperature'>
*     <CalDate>2023-02-18</CalDate>
*     <a0>-1.268043E-03</a0>
*     <a1>3.490084E-04</a1>
*     <a2>-6.664759E-06</a2>
*     <a3>2.024966E-07</a3>
*     <OFFSET>0.000000E+00</OFFSET>
*   </Calibration>
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
* <EventSummary DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606983'>
*   <EventList numEvents='0' maxStack='-2'>
*   </EventList>
* </EventSummary>
*
* </InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
* ** WHOTS 19 BOW 180 DEG - 110 CM BELOW DECK
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 4
# nvalues = 530243
# units = specified

```

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```

# name 0 = scan: Scan Count
# name 1 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 2 = t090C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C
# name 3 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 1, 530243
# span 1 = 157.041667, 525.265266
# span 2 = 0.0280, 34.3724
# span 3 = 0.000e+00, 0.000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jun 06 2023 01:00:00
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# sensor 0 = RRatio temperature, 05606983
# datcnv_date = Jun 08 2024 18:22:20, SeatermUSB v 1.8.2
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE56\SBE56_6983.xml
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 7211
* <?xml version="1.0"?>
* <!--DeviceManager-->
* <SBEDataUploadFile>
* <ApplicationData>
* <DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.8.2</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>25-Jul-2018 07:49:42 UTC</BuildDate>
* </DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607211'>
* <DateTime>2024-06-08T06:48:31</DateTime>
* <DelayedStart>2023-06-06T01:00:00</DelayedStart>
* <EventSummary numEvents='0' />
* <Power>
* <MainSupplyVoltage>3.67</MainSupplyVoltage>
* </Power>
* <ADCRatio>
* <Ratio>7122864</Ratio>
* </ADCRatio>
* <Battery>
* <Installed>2023-05-01T19:36:24</Installed>
* <Samples>530267</Samples>
* </Battery>
* <MemorySummary>
* <Samples>530267</Samples>
* <Bytes>2207744</Bytes>
* <BytesFree>64376832</BytesFree>
* </MemorySummary>
* </StatusData>
*
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607211'>
* <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc</Manufacturer>
* <FirmwareVersion>SBE56 V0.98</FirmwareVersion>
* <FirmwareDate>May 7 2019</FirmwareDate>
* <PCBAAssembly PCBID='112206' AssemblyNum='41688F' />
* <MfgDate>Feb 25 2011</MfgDate>

```

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```

*   <PCBType>0</PCBType>
*   <InternalSensors>
*     <Sensor id='Water Temperature'>
*       <type>TEMP0</type>
*       <SerialNumber>05607211</SerialNumber>
*     </Sensor>
*   </InternalSensors>
* </HardwareData>
*
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607211'>
*   <Settings
*     samplePeriod='60' format='1' />
* </ConfigurationData>
*
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607211'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMP0' id='Water Temperature'>
*     <CalDate>2023-02-18</CalDate>
*     <a0>-1.394984E-03</a0>
*     <a1>3.594659E-04</a1>
*     <a2>-6.970733E-06</a2>
*     <a3>2.124364E-07</a3>
*     <OFFSET>0.000000E+00</OFFSET>
*   </Calibration>
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
* <EventSummary DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607211'>
*   <EventList numEvents='0' maxStack='-2'>
*     </EventList>
* </EventSummary>
*
* </InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
* ** WHOTS 19 PORT 120 DEG - 80 CM BELOW DECK
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 4
# nvalues = 530267
# units = specified
# name 0 = scan: Scan Count
# name 1 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 2 = t090C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C
# name 3 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 1, 530267
# span 1 = 157.041667, 525.281933
# span 2 = -0.0033, 35.3820
# span 3 = 0.000e+00, 0.000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jun 06 2023 01:00:00
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# sensor 0 = RRatio temperature, 05607211
# datchv_date = Jun 08 2024 18:22:30, SeatermUSB v 1.8.2
# datchv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE56\SBE56_7211.xml
# datchv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

```

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```
# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3382
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\danfi\Desktop\whots-19_mcats\w19_015m_3382.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3382
* Conductivity SN = 3382
* System Upload Time = Jun 11 2024 00:14:29
** whots-19
** 15m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3382 06-11-2024 00:13:21
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenum = 174243, free = 58773
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 15.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 19.73 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3382
* temperature: 14-apr-23
*   TAO = -1.641162e-05
*   TA1 = 2.809134e-04
*   TA2 = -2.678836e-06
*   TA3 = 1.658588e-07
* conductivity: 14-apr-23
*   G = -1.015468e+00
*   H = 1.414975e-01
*   I = -1.302092e-04
*   J = 3.535856e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -6.932923e-06
* rtc: 14-apr-23
*   RTCA0 = 9.999800e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.786062e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.301592e-08

* S>
*END*
```

```
# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6892
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-19_recovery\w19_007m_6892.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
```

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```
* Temperature SN = 6892
* Conductivity SN = 6892
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 08 2024 09:39:21
* sample interval = 75 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706892'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41647</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41610B</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>16 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706892</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706892</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*       <type>strain-0</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>2651324</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*   </InternalSensors>
```

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```
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706892'>
*
*   <DateTime>2024-06-08T04:46:41</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='9' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 7.00</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.15</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*     <Bytes>6224205</Bytes>
*
*     <Samples>414947</Samples>
*
*     <SamplesFree>144293</SamplesFree>
*
*     <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706892'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*   <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*   <SampleInterval>75</SampleInterval>
*
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706892'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706892</SerialNum>
*
*   </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
```

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```
*      <CalDate>14-Apr-23</CalDate>
*
*      <A0>6.752063e-05</A0>
*
*      <A1>2.680171e-04</A1>
*
*      <A2>-1.983505e-06</A2>
*
*      <A3>1.393184e-07</A3>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='WBCONDO' id='Conductivity'>
*
*      <SerialNum>03706892</SerialNum>
*
*      <CalDate>14-Apr-23</CalDate>
*
*      <G>-1.015170e+00</G>
*
*      <H>1.481606e-01</H>
*
*      <I>-8.220501e-05</I>
*
*      <J>2.843512e-05</J>
*
*      <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*      <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*      <WBOTC>1.282297e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*      <SerialNum>2651324</SerialNum>
*
*      <CalDate>12-Apr-23</CalDate>
*
*      <PA0>2.575698e-01</PA0>
*
*      <PA1>5.037208e-03</PA1>
*
*      <PA2>-9.188744e-12</PA2>
*
*      <PTCA0>5.248322e+05</PTCA0>
*
*      <PTCA1>4.401518e+00</PTCA1>
*
*      <PTCA2>-9.524952e-02</PTCA2>
*
*      <PTCB0>2.625875e+01</PTCB0>
*
*      <PTCB1>-6.500000e-04</PTCB1>
*
```

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```

*      <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
*      <PTempa0>-7.111706e+01</PTempa0>
*
*      <PTempa1>4.915885e-02</PTempa1>
*
*      <PTempa2>-2.264329e-07</PTempa2>
*
*      <POFFSET>0.000000e+00</POFFSET>
*
*      <PRANGE>1.450000e+03</PRANGE>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706892'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='9' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='3' />
*
*   <Event type='alarm long' count='6' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** WHOTS18 whots-19
** 55m 7m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 414947
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 0.000032, 5.553009
# span 1 = 0.4905, 31.7238
# span 2 = -0.248, 17.286
# span 3 = 165.000000, 525.196725
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 75
# start_time = Jun 14 2023 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6892</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>14-Apr-23</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>6.75206300e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.68017100e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-1.98350500e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.39318400e-007</A3>

```

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```

#     <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#     <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#   </TemperatureSensor>
# </sensor>
# <sensor Channel="2" >
#   <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#   <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#     <SerialNumber>6892</SerialNumber>
#     <CalibrationDate>14-Apr-23</CalibrationDate>
#     <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#     <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#     <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#     <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#     <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#     <Coefficients equation="0" >
#       <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#       <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#       <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#       <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#       <M>0.0</M>
#       <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#     </Coefficients>
#     <Coefficients equation="1" >
#       <G>-1.01517000e+000</G>
#       <H>1.48160600e-001</H>
#       <I>-8.22050100e-005</I>
#       <J>2.84351200e-005</J>
#       <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#       <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#       <WBOTC>1.28229700e-007</WBOTC>
#     </Coefficients>
#     <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#     <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#   </ConductivitySensor>
# </sensor>
# <sensor Channel="3" >
#   <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
#   <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
#     <SerialNumber>2651324</SerialNumber>
#     <CalibrationDate>12-Apr-23</CalibrationDate>
#     <PA0>2.57569800e-001</PA0>
#     <PA1>5.03720800e-003</PA1>
#     <PA2>-9.18874400e-012</PA2>
#     <PTempa0>-7.11170600e+001</PTempa0>
#     <PTempa1>4.91588500e-002</PTempa1>
#     <PTempa2>-2.26432900e-007</PTempa2>
#     <PTCA0>5.24832200e+005</PTCA0>
#     <PTCA1>4.40151800e+000</PTCA1>
#     <PTCA2>-9.52495200e-002</PTCA2>
#     <PTCB0>2.62587500e+001</PTCB0>
#     <PTCB1>-6.50000000e-004</PTCB1>
#     <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
#     <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
#   </PressureSensor>
# </sensor>

```

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```
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 13 2024 14:38:03, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots19_mooring\wh19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_
↳microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\w19_007m_6892.hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\
↳whots19_mooring\wh19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\w19_007m_
↳6892.xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 4663
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-19_recovery\w19_025m_4663.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 4663
* Conductivity SN = 4663
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 08 2024 03:41:26
** whots-19
** 25m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 4663 06-08-2024 03:40:13
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenummer = 172873, free = 60143
* transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 25.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 23.08 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 4663
* temperature: 14-apr-23
* TAO = -3.651114e-05
* TA1 = 2.838335e-04
* TA2 = -2.961921e-06
* TA3 = 1.728443e-07
* conductivity: 14-apr-23
* G = -1.003258e+00
* H = 1.345263e-01
* I = -1.429068e-04
* J = 3.196058e-05
* CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
* CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
* WBOTC = -1.627869e-05
* rtc: 14-apr-23
* RTCA0 = 9.999873e-01
* RTCA1 = 1.636624e-06
* RTCA2 = -3.073115e-08
```

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```
* S>
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3633
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-19_recovery\w19_035m_3633.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3633
* Conductivity SN = 3633
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 07 2024 19:34:28
** whots19
** 035m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3633 06-07-2024 19:32:50
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenummer = 172710, free = 60306
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 35.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 19.58 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3633
* temperature: 14-apr-23
* TAO = -2.768427e-05
* TA1 = 2.835877e-04
* TA2 = -2.872635e-06
* TA3 = 1.707177e-07
* conductivity: 14-apr-23
* G = -1.019303e+00
* H = 1.249950e-01
* I = -6.729279e-05
* J = 2.582730e-05
* CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
* CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
* WBOTC = -1.458610e-05
* rtc: 14-apr-23
* RTCA0 = 9.999830e-01
* RTCA1 = 1.612749e-06
* RTCA2 = -3.153742e-08

* S>
*END*
```

```
# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3381
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\18082\Desktop\WHOTS-19_mcats\w19_040m_3381_redownload.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3381
* Conductivity SN = 3381
* System Upload Time = Jun 14 2024 22:52:39
** whots-19
** 40m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6a SERIAL NO. 3381 06-14-2024 22:51:54
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenum = 172866, free = 60150
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 40.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 20.12 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6a 3381
* temperature: 14-apr-23
* TAO = -3.247691e-05
* TA1 = 2.858018e-04
* TA2 = -2.966298e-06
* TA3 = 1.760258e-07
* conductivity: 14-apr-23
* G = -1.010994e+00
* H = 1.361200e-01
* I = -1.202721e-04
* J = 3.127186e-05
* CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
* CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
* WBOTC = -7.273084e-06
* rtc: 14-apr-23
* RTCA0 = 9.999795e-01
* RTCA1 = 1.763587e-06
* RTCA2 = -3.197946e-08

* S>
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3668
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-19_recovery\w19_045m_3668.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3668
* Conductivity SN = 3668
* System Upload Time = Jun 08 2024 03:10:09
```

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```
** whots-19
** 45m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3668 06-08-2024 03:08:40
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenum = 171871, free = 18779
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 22.92 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3668
* temperature: 14-apr-23
*   TAO = -1.672365e-04
*   TA1 = 3.004901e-04
*   TA2 = -3.860882e-06
*   TA3 = 1.903495e-07
* conductivity: 14-apr-23
*   G = -1.035126e+00
*   H = 1.343027e-01
*   I = -7.020420e-05
*   J = 2.705898e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -1.218318e-05
* pressure S/N 5579, range = 1450 psia: 18-apr-23
*   PA0 = -1.426169e-01
*   PA1 = 6.859640e-02
*   PA2 = -2.686288e-09
*   PTCA0 = -1.108384e+03
*   PTCA1 = -2.486515e-01
*   PTCA2 = 7.003375e-03
*   PTCSB0 = 2.492287e+01
*   PTCSB1 = 3.750000e-04
*   PTCSB2 = 0.000000e+00
*   POFSET = 0.000000e+00
* rtc: 14-apr23
*   RTCA0 = 9.999746e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.727574e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.404602e-08

* S>
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3619
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\danfi\Desktop\whots-19_mcats\w19_050m_3619.asc
```

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```
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3619
* Conductivity SN = 3619
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 11 2024 00:20:21
** whots-19
** 50m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3619 06-11-2024 00:19:06
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenum = 174245, free = 58771
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 50.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 20.00 deg C
```

```
* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3619
* temperature: 18-apr-23
*   TAO = -1.251457e-04
*   TA1 = 2.839028e-04
*   TA2 = -2.620611e-06
*   TA3 = 1.569759e-07
* conductivity: 18-apr-23
*   G = -9.946066e-01
*   H = 1.356605e-01
*   I = -6.729854e-05
*   J = 2.731227e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -8.184573e-06
* rtc: 18-apr-23
*   RTCA0 = 9.999782e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.690207e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.328952e-08
```

```
* S>
*END*
```

```
# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3620
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\18082\Desktop\WHOTS-19_mcats\w19_055m_3620.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3620
* Conductivity SN = 3620
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 11 2024 00:02:11
** whots-19
```

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```
** 55m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3620 06-11-2024 00:01:23
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenum = 174240, free = 58776
* transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 55.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 19.91 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3620
* temperature: 14-apr-23
*   TAO = -5.229356e-05
*   TA1 = 2.839673e-04
*   TA2 = -2.957658e-06
*   TA3 = 1.706467e-07
* conductivity: 14-apr-23
*   G = -1.011294e+00
*   H = 1.367751e-01
*   I = -1.074528e-04
*   J = 2.917739e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -1.068942e-05
* rtc: 14-apr-23
*   RTCA0 = 9.999726e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.710818e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.067796e-08

* S>
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3621
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\18082\Desktop\WHOTS-19_mcats\w19_065m_3621.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3621
* Conductivity SN = 3621
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 10 2024 23:57:22
** whots-19
** 65m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3621 10 Jun 2024 23:56:24
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenum = 174238, free = 58778
```

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```
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 65.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 20.08 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3621
* temperature: 13-apr-23
*   TAO = -4.412578e-06
*   TA1 = 2.728183e-04
*   TA2 = -2.034944e-06
*   TA3 = 1.476782e-07
* conductivity: 13-apr-23
*   G = -1.011447e+00
*   H = 1.421872e-01
*   I = -8.956687e-05
*   J = 2.994932e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -1.146184e-05
* rtc: 13-apr-23
*   RTCA0 = 9.999853e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.633466e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.146521e-08

* S>
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 9988
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Documents and Settings\Administrator\Desktop\WHOTS-19_recovery\w19_075m_9988.
→hex
* Software version SeatermV2 1.1j
* Temperature SN = 9988
* Conductivity SN = 9988
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 07 2024 21:44:44
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.1j</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>14-May-2012</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03709988'>
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
```

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```

* <PCBAssembly>41647</PCBAssembly>
* <PCBAssembly>41624A</PCBAssembly>
* <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
* <MfgDate>8 Aug 2012</MfgDate>
* <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
* <InternalSensors>
*   <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*     <type>temperature-1</type>
*     <SerialNumber>03709988</SerialNumber>
*   </Sensor>
*   <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*     <type>conductivity-1</type>
*     <SerialNumber>03709988</SerialNumber>
*   </Sensor>
* </InternalSensors>
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03709988'>
*   <DateTime>2024-06-07T20:23:33</DateTime>
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*   <Power>
*     <vMain> 7.03</vMain>
*     <vLith> 3.15</vLith>
*   </Power>
*   <MemorySummary>
*     <Bytes>1727250</Bytes>
*     <Samples>172725</Samples>
*     <SamplesFree>666135</SamplesFree>
*     <SampleLength>10</SampleLength>
*   </MemorySummary>
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03709988'>
*   <PressureInstalled>no</PressureInstalled>
*   <ReferencePressure>7.500000e+01</ReferencePressure>
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*   <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*   <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*   <SampleInterval>180</SampleInterval>
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03709988'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*     <SerialNum>03709988</SerialNum>
*     <CalDate>14-Apr-23</CalDate>
*     <A0>-5.159456e-05</A0>
*     <A1>2.990909e-04</A1>
*     <A2>-4.019862e-06</A2>
*     <A3>1.901382e-07</A3>
*   </Calibration>
*   <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>
*     <SerialNum>03709988</SerialNum>
*     <CalDate>14-Apr-23</CalDate>
*     <G>-9.806384e-01</G>
*     <H>1.494975e-01</H>

```

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```

*      <I>-2.419426e-04</I>
*      <J>4.167856e-05</J>
*      <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*      <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*      <WBOTC>1.950041e-07</WBOTC>
*    </Calibration>
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03709988'>
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1'/>
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='1'/>
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** Cruise WHOTS-19
** depth 075m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 172725
# units = specified
# name 0 = cond0S/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prM: Pressure [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = -0.000029, 5.570318
# span 1 = 0.0666, 31.0193
# span 2 = 75.000, 75.000
# span 3 = 165.000000, 524.841667
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 180
# start_time = Jun 14 2023 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="2" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>9988</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>14-Apr-23</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>-5.15945600e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.99090900e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-4.01986200e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.90138200e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>9988</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>14-Apr-23</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>

```

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```

# <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
# <Coefficients equation="0" >
# <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
# <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
# <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
# <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
# <M>0.0</M>
# <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
# </Coefficients>
# <Coefficients equation="1" >
# <G>-9.80638400e-001</G>
# <H>1.49497500e-001</H>
# <I>-2.41942600e-004</I>
# <J>4.16785600e-005</J>
# <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
# <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
# <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
# <WBOTC>1.95004100e-007</WBOTC>
# </Coefficients>
# <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
# <Offset>0.00000</Offset>
# </ConductivitySensor>
# </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 13 2024 14:46:29, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots19_mooring\wh19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_
→microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\w19_075m_9988.hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\
→whots19_mooring\wh19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\w19_075m_
→9988.xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

```

```

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 4699
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\18082\Desktop\WHOTS-19_mcats\w19_085m_4699.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 4699
* Conductivity SN = 4699
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 10 2024 23:52:47
** whots-19
** 85m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 4699 06-10-2024 23:52:11
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 240 seconds
* samplenumber = 130678, free = 59972
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed

```

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```
* temperature = 19.95 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 4699
* temperature: 18-apr-23
*   TAO = -1.013771e-04
*   TA1 = 3.010984e-04
*   TA2 = -4.108606e-06
*   TA3 = 2.013147e-07
* conductivity: 18-apr-23
*   G = -9.962566e-01
*   H = 1.536107e-01
*   I = -3.242679e-04
*   J = 5.198756e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -5.814154e-06
* pressure S/N 10209, range = 1450 psia: 14-apr-23
*   PA0 = 9.275078e-02
*   PA1 = 6.895788e-02
*   PA2 = -2.741533e-09
*   PTCA0 = -1.988741e+02
*   PTCA1 = -6.124735e-02
*   PTCA2 = 6.054749e-03
*   PTCSB0 = 2.500238e+01
*   PTCSB1 = -7.250000e-04
*   PTCSB2 = 0.000000e+00
*   POFSET = 0.000000e+00
* rtc: 18-apr-23
*   RTCA0 = 9.999895e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.587011e-06
*   RTCA2 = -2.869577e-08

* S>
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3791
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\danfi\Documents\Work\WHOTS-19_recovery\w19_095m_3791.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3791
* Conductivity SN = 3791
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 07 2024 18:32:21
** whots-19
** 95m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3791 08 Jun 2024 04:30:58
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenum = 171890, free = 61126
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
```

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```
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 95.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 22.34 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3791
* temperature: 13-apr-23
*   TAO = 6.377279e-05
*   TA1 = 2.602906e-04
*   TA2 = -1.044213e-06
*   TA3 = 1.241293e-07
* conductivity: 13-apr-23
*   G = -1.017526e+00
*   H = 1.451710e-01
*   I = -4.207883e-05
*   J = 2.717897e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -1.284126e-05
* rtc: 13-apr-23
*   RTCA0 = 9.999860e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.626248e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.310045e-08

* S>
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 2769
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\danfi\Documents\Work\WHOTS-19_recovery\w19_105m_2769.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 2769
* Conductivity SN = 2769
* System Upload Time = Jun 07 2024 17:29:41
** whots-19
** 105m
* ds
* SBE37SM-RS232 v3.1 SERIAL NO. 2769 08 Jun 2024 03:29:05
* vMain = 6.99, vLith = 3.24
* samplenum = 129653, free = 429587
* not logging, stop command
* sample interval = 240 seconds
* data format = converted engineering
* output salinity
* transmit real-time = no
* sync mode = no
* pump installed = no

* S>
* SBE37SM-RS232 V 3.1 2769
```

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```

* temperature: 14-Apr-23
*   TAO = -6.862328e-05
*   TA1 = 2.887448e-04
*   TA2 = -3.347584e-06
*   TA3 = 1.794880e-07
* conductivity: 14-Apr-23
*   G = -9.912924e-01
*   H = 1.515118e-01
*   I = -3.536343e-04
*   J = 5.242402e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -5.550443e-06
* pressure S/N 12364705, range = 1450 psia 30-Dec-22
*   PA0 = -2.778723e-01
*   PA1 = 4.402441e-03
*   PA2 = -2.574813e-11
*   PTCA0 = 5.248191e+05
*   PTCA1 = 0.000000e+00
*   PTCA2 = -0.000000e+00
*   PTCB0 = 0.000000e+00
*   PTCB1 = 0.000000e+00
*   PTCB2 = 0.000000e+00
*   PTEMPA0 = 0.000000e+00
*   PTEMPA1 = 0.000000e+00
*   PTEMPA2 = 0.000000e+00
*   PPOFFSET = 0.000000e+00

* S>
*END*

```

```

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 25352
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\danfi\Documents\Work\WHOTS-19_recovery\w19_120m_25352.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 25352
* Conductivity SN = 25352
* System Upload Time = Jun 07 2024 16:00:07
* sample interval = 240 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03725352'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Scientific</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>6.3.2</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Oct 23 2020 11:20:38</FirmwareDate>
*

```

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```
* <CommandSetVersion>1.3</CommandSetVersion>
*
* <PCBAssembly SerialNum='274791' AssemblyNum='41661E' />
*
* <PCBAssembly SerialNum='274796' AssemblyNum='41783S' />
*
* <PCBAssembly SerialNum='274793' AssemblyNum='41785C' />
*
* <MfgDate>20Dec2022</MfgDate>
*
* <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37-232-V3 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
* <InternalSensors>
*
*   <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*     <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>03725352</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
*   <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*     <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>03725352</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
*   <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*     <type>strain-0</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>5983494</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
* </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03725352'>
*
*   <DateTime>2024-06-08T00:29:15</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='4' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain>13.27</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.20</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
```

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```

*
*   <Bytes>1944105</Bytes>
*
*   <Samples>129607</Samples>
*
*   <SamplesFree>429633</SamplesFree>
*
*   <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
* </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03725352'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <TemperatureUnits>Celsius</TemperatureUnits>
*
*   <ConductivityUnits>S/m</ConductivityUnits>
*
*   <PressureUnits>Decibar</PressureUnits>
*
*   <OutputTemperature>yes</OutputTemperature>
*
*   <OutputConductivity>yes</OutputConductivity>
*
*   <OutputPressure>yes</OutputPressure>
*
*   <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*   <OutputSC>no</OutputSC>
*
*   <SCCoeff>0.0200</SCCoeff>
*
*   <TxSampleNumber>no</TxSampleNumber>
*
*   <SampleInterval>240</SampleInterval>
*
*   <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
*   <LegacyMode>no</LegacyMode>
*
*   <CompatibleMode>yes</CompatibleMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03725352'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>

```

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```
*
*   <SerialNum>03725352</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>29-Dec-22</CalDate>
*
*   <A0>-1.634622e-04</A0>
*
*   <A1>3.080939e-04</A1>
*
*   <A2>-4.074424e-06</A2>
*
*   <A3>1.910542e-07</A3>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='WBCONDO' id='Conductivity'>
*
*   <SerialNum>03725352</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>29-Dec-22</CalDate>
*
*   <G>-1.018884e+00</G>
*
*   <H>1.599526e-01</H>
*
*   <I>-3.755003e-04</I>
*
*   <J>5.563778e-05</J>
*
*   <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*   <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*   <WBOTC>0.000000e+00</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*   <SerialNum>5983494</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>21-Dec-22</CalDate>
*
*   <PA0>-6.195061e-01</PA0>
*
*   <PA1>3.187571e-02</PA1>
*
*   <PA2>2.481354e-09</PA2>
*
*   <PTCA0>5.237722e+05</PTCA0>
*
*   <PTCA1>-5.299658e+00</PTCA1>
*
*   <PTCA2>2.049859e-01</PTCA2>
*
*   <PTCB0>9.862354e+01</PTCB0>
```

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```

*
*   <PTCB1>-2.586730e-03</PTCB1>
*
*   <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
*   <PTempa0>-9.150144e+01</PTempa0>
*
*   <PTempa1>3.829939e-02</PTempa1>
*
*   <PTempa2>1.238160e-06</PTempa2>
*
*   <POFFSET>0.000000e+00</POFFSET>
*
*   <PRANGE>1.015300e+04</PRANGE>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03725352'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='4' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='4' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** Cruise whots-19
** Depth 120m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 129607
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = -0.000009, 5.349136
# span 1 = 0.5170, 26.3224
# span 2 = -4.504, 123.285
# span 3 = 165.000000, 525.016667
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 240
# start_time = Jun 14 2023 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>25352</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>29-Dec-22</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>-1.63462200e-004</A0>
#       <A1>3.08093900e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-4.07442400e-006</A2>

```

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```

#       <A3>1.91054200e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>25352</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>29-Dec-22</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-1.01888400e+000</G>
#         <H>1.59952600e-001</H>
#         <I>-3.75500300e-004</I>
#         <J>5.56377800e-005</J>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#         <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#         <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#         <WBOTC>0.00000000e+000</WBOTC>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </ConductivitySensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="3" >
#     <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
#     <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
#       <SerialNumber>5983494</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>21-Dec-22</CalibrationDate>
#       <PA0>-6.19506100e-001</PA0>
#       <PA1>3.18757100e-002</PA1>
#       <PA2>2.48135400e-009</PA2>
#       <PTempa0>-9.15014400e+001</PTempa0>
#       <PTempa1>3.82993900e-002</PTempa1>
#       <PTempa2>1.23816000e-006</PTempa2>
#       <PTCA0>5.23772200e+005</PTCA0>
#       <PTCA1>-5.29965800e+000</PTCA1>
#       <PTCA2>2.04985900e-001</PTCA2>
#       <PTCB0>9.86235400e+001</PTCB0>
#       <PTCB1>-2.58673000e-003</PTCB1>
#       <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
#       <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
#     </PressureSensor>

```

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```

# </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 13 2024 14:47:27, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots19_mooring\wh19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_
↳microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\w19_120m_25352.hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\
↳whots19_mooring\wh19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\w19_120m_
↳25352.xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 25444
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\danfi\Documents\Work\WHOTS-19_recovery\w19_135m_25444.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 25444
* Conductivity SN = 25444
* System Upload Time = Jun 07 2024 14:15:20
* sample interval = 240 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03725444'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Scientific</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>6.3.2</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Oct 23 2020 11:20:38</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <CommandSetVersion>1.3</CommandSetVersion>
*
*   <PCBAAssembly SerialNum='274721' AssemblyNum='41661E' />
*
*   <PCBAAssembly SerialNum='274817' AssemblyNum='41783S' />
*
*   <PCBAAssembly SerialNum='274822' AssemblyNum='41785C' />
*
*   <MfgDate>22Dec2022</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37-232-V3 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03725444</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*

```

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```
*      <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*          <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*          <SerialNumber>03725444</SerialNumber>
*
*      </Sensor>
*
*      <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*          <type>strain-0</type>
*
*          <SerialNumber>12152941</SerialNumber>
*
*      </Sensor>
*
*  </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03725444'>
*
*   <DateTime>2024-06-07T22:44:09</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='2' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain>13.39</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.20</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*     <Bytes>1943715</Bytes>
*
*     <Samples>129581</Samples>
*
*     <SamplesFree>429659</SamplesFree>
*
*     <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03725444'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <TemperatureUnits>Celsius</TemperatureUnits>
*
```

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```

* <ConductivityUnits>S/m</ConductivityUnits>
*
* <PressureUnits>Decibar</PressureUnits>
*
* <OutputTemperature>yes</OutputTemperature>
*
* <OutputConductivity>yes</OutputConductivity>
*
* <OutputPressure>yes</OutputPressure>
*
* <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
* <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
* <OutputSC>no</OutputSC>
*
* <SCCoeff>0.0200</SCCoeff>
*
* <TxSampleNumber>no</TxSampleNumber>
*
* <SampleInterval>240</SampleInterval>
*
* <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
* <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* <LegacyMode>no</LegacyMode>
*
* <CompatibleMode>no</CompatibleMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03725444'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03725444</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>30-Dec-22</CalDate>
*
*     <A0>-1.463417e-04</A0>
*
*     <A1>3.120446e-04</A1>
*
*     <A2>-4.661027e-06</A2>
*
*     <A3>2.055070e-07</A3>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
*   <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03725444</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>30-Dec-22</CalDate>
*
*     <G>-1.004307e+00</G>

```

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```

*
*   <H>1.542670e-01</H>
*
*   <I>-3.258636e-04</I>
*
*   <J>4.855151e-05</J>
*
*   <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*   <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*   <WBOTC>2.282282e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*   <SerialNum>12152941</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>22-Dec-22</CalDate>
*
*   <PA0>1.338623e+00</PA0>
*
*   <PA1>3.179865e-02</PA1>
*
*   <PA2>-1.978555e-09</PA2>
*
*   <PTCA0>5.246397e+05</PTCA0>
*
*   <PTCA1>3.126805e+00</PTCA1>
*
*   <PTCA2>-1.035617e-01</PTCA2>
*
*   <PTCB0>2.521830e+01</PTCB0>
*
*   <PTCB1>-1.206030e-03</PTCB1>
*
*   <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
*   <PTempa0>-7.118709e+01</PTempa0>
*
*   <PTempa1>5.232046e-02</PTempa1>
*
*   <PTempa2>-7.376980e-07</PTempa2>
*
*   <POFFSET>0.000000e+00</POFFSET>
*
*   <PRANGE>1.015300e+04</PRANGE>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03725444'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='2' />
*

```

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```

*   <Event type='PON reset' count='2' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** Cruise whots-19
** Depth 135m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 129581
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 0.000003, 5.342637
# span 1 = 0.5230, 31.8500
# span 2 = -1.605, 138.236
# span 3 = 165.000000, 524.944444
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 240
# start_time = Jun 14 2023 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>25444</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>30-Dec-22</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>-1.46341700e-004</A0>
#       <A1>3.12044600e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-4.66102700e-006</A2>
#       <A3>2.05507000e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>25444</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>30-Dec-22</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>

```

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```

#     </Coefficients>
#     <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-1.00430700e+000</G>
#         <H>1.54267000e-001</H>
#         <I>-3.25863600e-004</I>
#         <J>4.85515100e-005</J>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#         <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#         <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#         <WBOTC>2.28228200e-007</WBOTC>
#     </Coefficients>
#     <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#     <Offset>0.00000</Offset>
# </ConductivitySensor>
# </sensor>
# <sensor Channel="3" >
#     <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
#     <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
#         <SerialNumber>52941</SerialNumber>
#         <CalibrationDate>22-Dec-22</CalibrationDate>
#         <PA0>1.33862300e+000</PA0>
#         <PA1>3.17986500e-002</PA1>
#         <PA2>-1.97855500e-009</PA2>
#         <PTempa0>-7.11870900e+001</PTempa0>
#         <PTempa1>5.23204600e-002</PTempa1>
#         <PTempa2>-7.37698000e-007</PTempa2>
#         <PTCA0>5.24639700e+005</PTCA0>
#         <PTCA1>3.12680500e+000</PTCA1>
#         <PTCA2>-1.03561700e-001</PTCA2>
#         <PTCB0>2.52183000e+001</PTCB0>
#         <PTCB1>-1.20603000e-003</PTCB1>
#         <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
#         <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
#     </PressureSensor>
# </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 13 2024 14:47:46, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots19_mooring\wh19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_
→microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\w19_135m_25444.hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\
→whots19_mooring\wh19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\WHOTS-19_microcat_data\w19_135m_
→25444.xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 4701
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Documents and Settings\Administrator\Desktop\WHOTS-19_recovery\w19_155m_4701_
→2ndtry.asc
* Software Version 1.58
* Temperature SN = 4701
* Conductivity SN = 4701
* System Upload Time = Jun 08 2024 03:43:54
** whots-19
** 155m
* ds

```

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```
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 4701 08 Jun 2024 03:42:44
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 240 seconds
* samplenum = 129571, free = 61079
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 23.28 deg C
```

```
* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 4701
* temperature: 18-apr-23
*   TAO = 2.105019e-05
*   TA1 = 2.749298e-04
*   TA2 = -2.105408e-06
*   TA3 = 1.517139e-07
* conductivity: 18-apr-23
*   G = -1.006527e+00
*   H = 1.486128e-01
*   I = -2.362030e-05
*   J = 2.769558e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -9.383437e-06
* pressure S/N 10211, range = 1450 psia: 14-apr-23
*   PA0 = -5.075048e-02
*   PA1 = 6.946433e-02
*   PA2 = -1.651236e-08
*   PTCA0 = -1.961793e+02
*   PTCA1 = -3.413052e-01
*   PTCA2 = 1.479438e-02
*   PTCSB0 = 2.496538e+01
*   PTCSB1 = -1.925000e-03
*   PTCSB2 = 0.000000e+00
*   POFSET = -6.300000e-02
* rtc: 18-apr-23
*   RTCA0 = 9.999870e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.789222e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.228207e-08
```

```
* S>
*END*
```

```
# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 11381
```

```
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE37\SBE37_11381.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 11381
```

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```
* Conductivity SN = 11381
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 08 2024 00:14:52
* sample interval = 300 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711381'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41647.1</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41610B</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>19-Oct-2013</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03711381</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03711381</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*       <type>strain-0</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>2146836</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*   </InternalSensors>
*
```

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```

* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711381'>
*
*   <DateTime>2024-06-07T23:02:10</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 6.92</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.23</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*     <Bytes>1546395</Bytes>
*
*     <Samples>103093</Samples>
*
*     <SamplesFree>456147</SamplesFree>
*
*     <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711381'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <OutputSalinity>no</OutputSalinity>
*
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*   <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*   <SampleInterval>300</SampleInterval>
*
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711381'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03711381</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>10-Feb-23</CalDate>

```

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```
*
*   <A0>-7.840626e-05</A0>
*
*   <A1>3.019964e-04</A1>
*
*   <A2>-4.194832e-06</A2>
*
*   <A3>1.960253e-07</A3>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='WBCONDO' id='Conductivity'>
*
*   <SerialNum>03711381</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>10-Feb-23</CalDate>
*
*   <G>-9.817091e-01</G>
*
*   <H>1.392003e-01</H>
*
*   <I>-1.946812e-04</I>
*
*   <J>3.414003e-05</J>
*
*   <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*   <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*   <WBOTC>7.523668e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*   <SerialNum>2146836</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>07-Feb-23</CalDate>
*
*   <PA0>-1.437911e+01</PA0>
*
*   <PA1>3.134084e-02</PA1>
*
*   <PA2>9.389038e-10</PA2>
*
*   <PTCA0>5.300600e+05</PTCA0>
*
*   <PTCA1>-2.440445e+01</PTCA1>
*
*   <PTCA2>1.723165e-01</PTCA2>
*
*   <PTCB0>1.037944e+02</PTCB0>
*
*   <PTCB1>-7.587441e-03</PTCB1>
*
*   <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
```

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```

*
*   <PTEMPA0>-9.626943e+01</PTEMPA0>
*
*   <PTEMPA1>3.959023e-02</PTEMPA1>
*
*   <PTEMPA2>1.402931e-06</PTEMPA2>
*
*   <POFFSET>0.000000e+00</POFFSET>
*
*   <PRANGE>1.015300e+04</PRANGE>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711381'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
# nquan = 6
# nvalues = 103093
# units = specified
# name 0 = cond0S/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = sal00: Salinity, Practical [PSU]
# name 3 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 4 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 5 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 0.000009, 5.360072
# span 1 = 1.4718, 32.1715
# span 2 = 0.0018, 35.2484
# span 3 = -3.150, 4726.497
# span 4 = 167.000012, 524.958345
# span 5 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 300
# start_time = Jun 16 2023 00:00:01 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>11381</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>10-Feb-23</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>-7.84062600e-005</A0>
#       <A1>3.01996400e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-4.19483200e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.96025300e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >

```

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```

# <SerialNumber>11381</SerialNumber>
# <CalibrationDate>10-Feb-23</CalibrationDate>
# <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
# <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
# <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
# <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
# <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
# <Coefficients equation="0" >
# <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
# <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
# <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
# <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
# <M>0.0</M>
# <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
# </Coefficients>
# <Coefficients equation="1" >
# <G>-9.81709100e-001</G>
# <H>1.39200300e-001</H>
# <I>-1.94681200e-004</I>
# <J>3.41400300e-005</J>
# <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
# <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
# <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
# <WBOTC>7.52366800e-007</WBOTC>
# </Coefficients>
# <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
# <Offset>0.00000</Offset>
# </ConductivitySensor>
# </sensor>
# <sensor Channel="3" >
# <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
# <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
# <SerialNumber>2146836</SerialNumber>
# <CalibrationDate>07-Feb-23</CalibrationDate>
# <PA0>-1.43791100e+001</PA0>
# <PA1>3.13408400e-002</PA1>
# <PA2>9.38903800e-010</PA2>
# <PTEMPA0>-9.62694300e+001</PTEMPA0>
# <PTEMPA1>3.95902300e-002</PTEMPA1>
# <PTEMPA2>1.40293100e-006</PTEMPA2>
# <PTCA0>5.30060000e+005</PTCA0>
# <PTCA1>-2.44044500e+001</PTCA1>
# <PTCA2>1.72316500e-001</PTCA2>
# <PTCB0>1.03794400e+002</PTCB0>
# <PTCB1>-7.58744100e-003</PTCB1>
# <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
# <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
# </PressureSensor>
# </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnu_date = Jun 08 2024 00:27:19, 7.26.7.129 [datcnu_vars = 5]
# datcnu_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE37\sbe37_11381.hex
→ C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE37\SBE37_11381.xmlcon
# datcnu_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

```

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```

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 11380
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE37\SBE37_11380.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 11380
* Conductivity SN = 11380
* System Upload Time = Jun 08 2024 00:17:33
* sample interval = 300 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711380'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41647.1</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41610B</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>13-Nov-2013</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03711380</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03711380</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*       <type>strain-0</type>
*
*

```

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```
*      <SerialNumber>2146835</SerialNumber>
*
*      </Sensor>
*
*    </InternalSensors>
*
*  </HardwareData>
*  <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711380'>
*
*    <DateTime>2024-06-07T23:04:54</DateTime>
*
*    <EventSummary numEvents='4' />
*
*    <Power>
*
*      <vMain> 6.99</vMain>
*
*      <vLith> 2.99</vLith>
*
*    </Power>
*
*    <MemorySummary>
*
*      <Bytes>1546395</Bytes>
*
*      <Samples>103093</Samples>
*
*      <SamplesFree>456147</SamplesFree>
*
*      <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
*    </MemorySummary>
*
*    <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
*  </StatusData>
*  <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711380'>
*
*    <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*    <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*    <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*    <OutputSalinity>no</OutputSalinity>
*
*    <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*    <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*    <SampleInterval>300</SampleInterval>
*
*    <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
*  </ConfigurationData>
*  <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711380'>
```

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```
*
* <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*   <SerialNum>03711380</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>15-Feb-23</CalDate>
*
*   <A0>-1.086200e-04</A0>
*
*   <A1>3.084300e-04</A1>
*
*   <A2>-4.591820e-06</A2>
*
*   <A3>2.050536e-07</A3>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='WBCONDO' id='Conductivity'>
*
*   <SerialNum>03711380</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>15-Feb-23</CalDate>
*
*   <G>-9.942626e-01</G>
*
*   <H>1.398204e-01</H>
*
*   <I>-1.799830e-04</I>
*
*   <J>3.349853e-05</J>
*
*   <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*   <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*   <WBOTC>2.809963e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*   <SerialNum>2146835</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>09-Feb-23</CalDate>
*
*   <PA0>-8.778848e+00</PA0>
*
*   <PA1>3.111777e-02</PA1>
*
*   <PA2>2.103285e-09</PA2>
*
*   <PTCA0>5.288735e+05</PTCA0>
*
*   <PTCA1>-1.731807e+01</PTCA1>
*
*   <PTCA2>2.151018e-01</PTCA2>
```

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```

*
*   <PTCB0>1.011848e+02</PTCB0>
*
*   <PTCB1>-2.443741e-03</PTCB1>
*
*   <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
*   <PTempa0>-9.571512e+01</PTempa0>
*
*   <PTempa1>4.049506e-02</PTempa1>
*
*   <PTempa2>1.149109e-06</PTempa2>
*
*   <POFFSET>0.000000e+00</POFFSET>
*
*   <PRANGE>1.015300e+04</PRANGE>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711380'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='4' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='3' />
*
*   <Event type='alarm long' count='1' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
# nquan = 6
# nvalues = 103093
# units = specified
# name 0 = cond0S/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = sal00: Salinity, Practical [PSU]
# name 3 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 4 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 5 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = -0.000098, 5.359559
# span 1 = 1.4716, 33.0106
# span 2 = 0.0000, 35.2128
# span 3 = -1.888, 4739.908
# span 4 = 167.000012, 524.958345
# span 5 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 300
# start_time = Jun 16 2023 00:00:01 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>11380</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>15-Feb-23</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>-1.08620000e-004</A0>
#       <A1>3.08430000e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-4.59182000e-006</A2>

```

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```

#       <A3>2.05053600e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>11380</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>15-Feb-23</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-9.94262600e-001</G>
#         <H>1.39820400e-001</H>
#         <I>-1.79983000e-004</I>
#         <J>3.34985300e-005</J>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#         <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#         <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#         <WBOTC>2.80996300e-007</WBOTC>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </ConductivitySensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="3" >
#     <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
#     <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
#       <SerialNumber>2146835</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>09-Feb-23</CalibrationDate>
#       <PA0>-8.77884800e+000</PA0>
#       <PA1>3.11177700e-002</PA1>
#       <PA2>2.10328500e-009</PA2>
#       <PTempa0>-9.57151200e+001</PTempa0>
#       <PTempa1>4.04950600e-002</PTempa1>
#       <PTempa2>1.14910900e-006</PTempa2>
#       <PTCA0>5.28873500e+005</PTCA0>
#       <PTCA1>-1.73180700e+001</PTCA1>
#       <PTCA2>2.15101800e-001</PTCA2>
#       <PTCB0>1.01184800e+002</PTCB0>
#       <PTCB1>-2.44374100e-003</PTCB1>
#       <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
#       <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
#     </PressureSensor>

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```
# </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 08 2024 00:27:06, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 5]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE37\sbe37_11380.hex
↳C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W19\DATA\SBE37\SBE37_11380.xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*
```

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